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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

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D2.1 Pre-stakeholder mapping for LHs and LLs

Pre-stakeholder mapping for LHs and LLs

Summary

This document constitutes the Deliverable **D2.1 Pre-stakeholder mapping for LHs and LLs of InBestSoil** is the first output of Task 2.1 *Analysis and mapping of stakeholders for each LH and LL* in the frame of WP2, *Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning*. The deliverable collects the main insights and context narratives for the 7 Lighthouses and 2 Living Labs that will act as use cases for the project activities, as well as a preliminary approach to stakeholder groups' identification and engagement for each of these sites. The deliverable has been developed in consultation with all consortium partners, LH and LL coordinators, and it will **be updated as needed with a final updated deliverable (D2.3) in M18**.

The objective of InBestSoil is to **co-create a framework for investment in conservation and recovery of soil health**, by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem services delivered by a healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentives. This will allow for public and private organisations to provide economic value to their actions over soil health, codesign strategies with local stakeholders, and work collectively to deliver national and EU policy ambitions. InBestSoil will provide data, evidence, tools and models to assess how investment in soil health can contribute to the transition to a long-term resilient and sustainable use of soil, focusing on 7 Lighthouses and 2 Living Labs, which provides a total of **9 study areas across 4 biogeographic regions in Europe** (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, Mediterranean), and different land uses (agriculture, forest, urban, mining), as models for cocreation and co-design (multi-actor approach, responsible research and innovation and open science). InBestSoil is a 48-month project that started in January 2023, and it includes 19 partners from 10 European countries.

WP2, *Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning* will cover the entire project duration and its **main objective is to create and strengthen stakeholder communities along the project LHs and LLs** as a central hub for the performance of all other WPs. WP2 is divided in four tasks to achieve the following specific objectives: [1] engage and involve a wide variety of local, regional, national and European stakeholders including companies, public authorities, investors and civil society in investments in soil health; [2] establish short- and long-term collaboration schemes and platforms for the effective co-creation, co-innovation and co-learning process and sustainability of the project by dynamizing LH communities and building LLs around them; and [3] implement participation, co-design and co-creation methodologies to fully integrate key stakeholders knowledge, perceptions and interests in all the project activities and beyond.

Assessing the economic value of ecosystem services provided by soil, as well as current initiatives in place for improving soil health, will need a wide variety of experts to determine the most successful factors that look for an equilibrium across all actors from the value chain, including civil society. Likewise, proposing new business models and policy recommendations or incentive frameworks will also benefit from the different perspectives that a diversity of stakeholders can bring to the table. Therefore, WP2 will **establish the most appropriate stakeholder groups that influence or are impacted by each LH and LL** of the project to enable effective co-creation initiatives in order to share information, upskill, and advance the general knowledge on soil management and investment models in the future.

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Introduction and scope

The D2.1 deliverable is the first output of task 2.1, *Analysis and mapping of stakeholders for each Lighthouse (LH) and Living Lab (LL)* in the frame of WP2. This task is led by ZABALA and involves all project partners, mainly LH and LL representatives within the consortium, to ensure that stakeholders are adequately identified and mapped.

The main objective of task 2.1 is to identify and map stakeholder communities along the project LHs and LLs, to ensure the economic value proposition, business models, and incentives framework proposed by InBestSoil meet real context needs. In addition, synergies with sister projects funded under the topic *HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-03: Soil biodiversity and its contribution to ecosystem services*, and other EU projects related to soil health management will be sought.

Within this task, ZABALA, together with project partners, has performed a **preliminary identification of relevant stakeholders related to each LH and LL involved in the project**, focusing on stakeholder group profiles and the type of knowledge they can bring or request from the project. In a second phase (D2.2, M18), these stakeholders will be categorised and mapped according to their interest in or influence on the project.

To better understand the potential interest and influence of stakeholders in relation to InBestSoil, high-level research on the context narrative for each LH and LL has been carried out, including key attributes and values including socioeconomic, culture and history aspects relevant to each location and within the Mission Soil framework. This analysis will be useful to carry out task 2.2 *Development of key stakeholders' co-design and co-creation plan and implementation roadmap* by understanding the different stakeholder groups' contexts in each location and best adapting co-design and co-creation activities to stakeholders' needs, as well as aligning these with Mission Soil objectives.

Relation to other project activities

WP2 shares objectives with all other project WPs as its main objective is to support the stakeholder engagement needs of the project to deliver on its expected results. To this aim, a preliminary stakeholder engagement needs roadmap has been developed, that includes all the expected stakeholder interactions needed by all WPs included in the project:

Figure 1. Stakeholder engagement activities and interactions included in project WPs.

Mission Soil: A Soil Deal for Europe

A Soil Deal for Europe (Mission Soil) is a major instrument to co-design, assess, monitor, and implement actions to restore and protect soil so that it can continuously provide benefits to society and the planet. The Mission not only aims to maximize the benefits of soil health conservation and restoration in the EU, but also to minimize the adverse effects of land use outside the EU, and it will largely contribute to the overall goals of the European Green Deal.

The Mission's **specific objectives** include:

Figure 2. InBestSoil's representation of Mission Soil specific objectives as indicated in the implementation plan¹.

The Mission will be implemented through:

- A **transdisciplinary research and innovation (R&I)** programme which includes a social science component to fill knowledge gaps and develop solutions for soil health. The Mission will address all types of land use in rural and urban areas.
- A **network of 100 Living Labs** (for experimentation) and **lighthouses** (for demonstration) to accelerate the co-creation and uptake of solutions across various settings in a diversified geographic and socio-economic context.
- A robust, harmonised **EU framework for soil monitoring and reporting**.
- **Communication and citizen engagement activities** to increase soil literacy across society.

To achieve these ambitious goals the Mission Soil wants to establish a **well-structured and participatory Governance structure** to which InBestSoil aims to contribute through its stakeholder engagement approach:

Figure 3. Mission Soil Governance structure (from Mission Soil Implementation Plan).

¹ [soil_mission_implementation_plan_final_for_publication.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

InBestSoil will establish connections with strategy, programming, and management bodies as well as with stakeholders involved in the implementation of the Mission. The project counts on 7 Lighthouses and 2 Living Labs, whose experience will provide the essential knowledge to set up the field for the creation of 3 new Living Labs, as well as a well-documented process for others to come (Task 2.4. From local to regional/national: building LLs based on existing LHs).

Stakeholder and citizen engagement in Mission Soil

The European Commission has promoted the Mission Soil and its objectives to interested stakeholders and citizens through several initiatives, thus facilitating their involvement and engagement in the Mission. **Awareness of soil issues is key to ensuring active position/participation and involvement** on the part of interested parties in activities and initiatives related to soil health.²

Stakeholder engagement is an essential pillar of the mission's added value that proposes a novel approach to R&I for impact. This is based on open science and interactive, **participatory innovation with strong stakeholder and citizen engagement (incl. through Living Labs and lighthouses)**. By implementing R&I activities, local testing grounds, monitoring and training activities in joint up manner, the mission will act as a broker of innovation and will go well beyond what could be achieved within single parts of Horizon Europe or other instruments at EU level. Also, the mission is expected to mobilise actors across society in ways that would not happen otherwise. All these aspects are contemplated within the Mission Soil Implementation plan operational objectives which InBestSoil aligns completely with:

Figure 4. Mission Soil Operational Objectives as set out within the implementation plan.

Thus, the identification, mapping, and consideration of all stakeholders in soil-related matters are of utmost importance. Recognizing the significance of their perspectives, the engagement of diverse stakeholders is crucial for comprehensive decision-making processes. By involving government bodies, local communities, scientists, environmental organisations, farmers, and industry representatives, we can foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and collective action towards sustainable soil management. **InBestSoil believes that each stakeholder brings unique expertise, interests, and concerns to the table, enriching the dialogue and enabling the development of holistic solutions that address the diverse challenges faced by our soils.** By actively involving all stakeholders, we can promote transparency, equity, and accountability, ensuring that decisions regarding soil health are well-informed, balanced, and sustainable in the long term.

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Communication and citizen engagement initiatives in line with the Horizon Europe Mission A Soil Deal for Europe – Report on dissemination and exploitation practices in Member States and associated countries*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/704413>

InBestSoil LH and LLs: A context narrative

Over 60% of European soils are currently in an unhealthy state and scientific evidence shows that soils are further degrading due to unsustainable management of the land, sealing, contamination and overexploitation, combined with the impact of climate change and extreme weather events. Degraded soils reduce the provision of ecosystem services such as food, feed, fibre, timber, nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, pest control or water regulation. The loss of these essential soil ecosystem services costs the EU at least 50 billion euro per year³. However, **activities that affect soil are not reported** as such in companies' environmental reporting standards, or appear mixed in with other statistics (Davies, 2017). To address soil health issues, the business sector, policymakers, public administration, and scientific community must join efforts to develop practices and policies that recognize and acknowledge the importance of soil for sustaining livelihoods, upholding biodiversity, and regulating earth's climate.

InBestSoil will define the monetary value of ecosystem services delivered by a healthy soil, analyse and upscale current successful business models, co-design with a wide range of stakeholders' new business models and initiatives based on the value of soil health, and propose appropriate incentives. This will lead to the creation of products, services and value chains that are less harmful to the soil. So far, soil health has never been conceived as an element for business models and investments.

To achieve this, InBestSoil has selected 7 existing Lighthouses (LH) and 2 Living Labs (LL, in different maturity stages) covering four different land uses (agricultural, forestry, urban and mining) across four different biogeographic regions in Europe (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic and Mediterranean). This diversity of use cases will enable project results to be replicable and adaptable to multiple areas across the EU.

The 7 LHs (forests, urban plots, and former mining areas) are examples of demonstration solutions and engagement of practitioners and key stakeholders to accelerate the innovation uptake. Each of the 2 LLs includes between 10 and 20 farms that operate at a subregional level, in which experiments involving land managers, farmers, farmers' organisations, businesses, scientific community, policymakers, and industries, among others, are coordinated to test, monitor, and evaluate practical solutions to develop business models with interventions that enhance soil health.

Figure 5. Map of InBestSoil Lighthouses and Living Labs

This section provides the main insights and context narratives for the LHs and LLs that will act as use cases for the InBestSoil project activities.

³ [Soil health \(europa.eu\)](https://soilhealth.europa.eu/)

A summary of the main characteristics of each Lighthouse and Living Lab participating in the project is presented below:

INBESTSOIL LIGHTHOUSES

LH	Location	Soil type	Land use	Challenges addressed	Since	Proposed solutions / Opportunities
LH1 - Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván	Extremadura, Spain	Mediterranean forestry (pasture) soil	Livestock farming, Agriculture	Poor land use and loss of fertility	1993	Carbon storage opportunities in forest soils Increased fertility and quality of soil through herbivores "carbon pump" and "rotational grazing"
LH2 - Saelices El Chico mine	Salamanca, Spain	Mediterranean Industrial Soil	Old Uranium mine	Overexploitation, soil abandonment, loss of structure and polluted flood risk near urban areas.	2006	Restored using artificial soils: technosols
LH3 - El Touro mine	Galicia, Spain	Atlantic Industrial soil	Old copper mine	Profound degradation of the environment, lack of vegetation and soil cover, rapid oxidation generating a hyper-acidic mine drainage which contaminates the nearby rivers	1989	Restored using artificial soils: technosols
LH4 - Peri urban soils Zagreb	Zagreb, Croatia	Continental Urban soil	Forest, Apple Orchard, Abandoned agricultural land, Grassland	Overexploitation, soil abandonment, compaction, and flood risk near urban areas	1991	Promoting sustainable natural processes: mulching, low soil disturbance, maintaining vegetation cover
LH5 - Baltupiai urban gardens	Vilnius, Lithuania	Boreal urban soil	Urban gardens, recreation	Poor land use, and risk of soil erosion and flooding in urban areas	2001	Flood regulation, Erosion regulation, Food production, Carbon sequestration, Recreation
LH6 - Mežole Forest	Vidzeme, Latvia	Boreal Forestry soil	Forests, recreation area	Diverse soil organic matter content, Unbalanced soil nutrient content, Soil acidification, Soil erosion on slopes	2001	Forest fertilization experiments, Forest regeneration on slopes and lowland parts, Natural and human promoted afforestation
LH7 - Atlantic Agricultural Soil	Betuwe, Netherlands	Atlantic agricultural soil	Agriculture	Reduced soil fertility, biodiversity and ecosystem services and need to extend crop diversifications	2008	Minimize the time in which the soil is bare; Alternative organic fertilization; developing business cases around N-fixing crops;

Table 1. Summary of InBestSoil Lighthouses' characteristics.

INBESTSOIL LIVING LABS

LL	Structure	Location	Soil type	Land use	Challenges addressed	Since	Proposed solutions / Opportunities
LL1 - Campidano plains & other Sardinian areas	2 LH 9 sites /Regional	Sardinia, Italy	Mediterranean Agricultural soil	Agriculture	Reduced soil fertility, biodiversity and ecosystem services associated with conventional agriculture	2003	Conservation agriculture
LL2 - Climate protection through humus build-up.	2 LH (among 10) 15 sites (among 55) / Regional	Basel land Canton, Switzerland	Continental agricultural soil	Agriculture	Intensive agriculture depletes SOM and increases the risk of soil erosion and loss of soil biodiversity.	2021	C-farming + C-credits

Table 2. Summary of InBestSoil Living Labs' characteristics.

LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil - Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván (El Baldío)

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Fundación Global Nature & Actyva
LH name (location)	Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván
Region	Talaván (Cáceres), Extremadura
Country	Spain
Area (Ha)	5.94 ha of best conditions (total area 232ha)
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No vegetative growth all year round • No humidity and temperature conditions for the necessary microbiological activity • Continuous degradation

LH Representatives

Fundación Global Nature (FGN) is an NGO focused on nature protection and conservation since 1993, based on technical rigor, ethical compromise, and innovation, distributed in 3 main blocks: habitat and species conservation, agricultural sector sustainability and corporate sustainability.

FGN works with the primary sector and the local population, with administrations, science, universities, and large companies, for creating alliances for the sustainable use of biodiversity and the natural heritage. FGN bridges theory and practice by combining the development of strategies and plans with fieldwork and applied projects. FGN works actively on the ground, through land stewardship agreements, stakeholders' involvement, and monitoring key indicators, to protect habitats and species.

The ACTYVA Cooperative Society is an initiative that arises to facilitate the generation of productive, alternative and solidarity economy projects, and the connections between them and with their immediate environment to reactivate relationships and exchanges at the local level from Extremadura. ACTYVA seeks to be an economic activation network from which to work at all levels and in all sectors, create synergies and advance models and comprehensive self-management solutions that generate benefits (personal, social, and environmental) for the environment and the community where they develop.

These two organisations have joined forces within the InBestSoil project to showcase the exemplary performance of the InBestSoil Lighthouse 1 (LH1) El Baldío de Talaván, a space at the service of biodiversity.

Geoclimatic description

The term 'dehesa' has many meanings. Nowadays, the most widely accepted definition is that of an agrosilvopastoral system developed on poor or non-agricultural land and aimed at extensive livestock raising.

The Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván is a property located between the Mediterranean mountain of Monfragüe and the plains area of the Llanos in Cáceres, spanning over 232 hectares of land, which has been managed by Fundación Global Nature since 1993.

The dehesa, a unique ecosystem in the Iberian Peninsula, is the focus of work at El Baldío, aimed at enhancing knowledge through partnerships and cross-cutting projects.

In this collaborative space, livestock farming, agriculture, and nature conservation coexist, promoting a sustainable business model for agriculture production and soil conservation. The exploration of new practices and approaches in the agri-livestock sector carried out in El Baldío, such as rotational grazing, enclosure rotation, and transhumance, have yielded positive outcomes. Collaborative work is ongoing, involving technical and educational visits, participation in various research projects led by FGN, and special attention to the preservation of native breeds.

Figure 6. Geographic location of LH1.

Socioeconomic description

Agricultural activity is the main economic sector in Talaván: in 2006, the percentage of employees in the primary sector was 35.59% of the population, which represents about a third of the active population.

In 2004, farms dedicated to agriculture accounted for 76.5% of the total. Most of them were dryland farming (74.9%). The main crops are olive trees (44.8%), cereals, especially oats (25.8%), forage crops (20%) and wheat (9.4%). Most of it is extensive agriculture.

EMPLOYMENT BY SECTOR	% of population
Primary sector	35.59%
Construction	22.37%
Industry	5.76%
Tertiary sector	35.93%

Table 3. Employment percentage per sector LH1 area (Talaván, Extremadura, Spain).

Identified challenges

In the EU, agriculture occupies more than 47% of the territory, and approximately 50% of European species depend on agricultural habitats. Such high natural value areas can generate social and economic value if well managed.

Soils in a Mediterranean context, such as in El Baldío, face extreme weather conditions such as high temperatures and water scarcity. Edaphic trophic dynamics in these contexts are impacted by:

- No vegetative growth all year round.
- No humidity and temperature conditions for the necessary microbiological activity.
- Continuous degradation.

In this context, Herbivores play a key role into maintaining these parameters at appropriate levels by activating the decomposition circuit of nutrients and microorganisms necessary for a healthy soil. Therefore, El Baldío implements grazing at a strategic level to:

- Preserve a high natural and agricultural value area by protecting endangered species.
- Protect species and biodiversity dependant on good management practices of the habitat.
- Direct interventions that generate natural, social, and economic value.

Proposed solution

"The Carbon Pump" with herbivorous animals emulates the operation of a pumping system to increase the availability of carbon and nutrients in the edaphic cycle dynamics:

- Phase I: grass growth, where the roots are the main contribution of carbon to the system.
- Phase II: herbivores eat the grass, thus activating a second phase of redistribution and drainage of the "pump", where the dead roots promote decomposition mechanisms that transform the residues into organic carbon.

The new recharge phase is activated when the increased availability of resources promotes new growth. The management of grazing pulses is essential to favour the charge and discharge cycles of the Carbon Pump and thus maintain the balance of the system.

Figure 7. Grazing management through the "Carbon Pump" in LH1.

The impact of the Carbon pump is increased when is combined with "rotational grazing", a grazing management system that limits the movements of big flocks of wild ungulates, generating exhaustive harvesting, a strong impact on pasture and soil, followed by sufficient recovery periods.

The "rotational grazing" approach leads to:

1. Lower input costs.
2. Increased production and quality of graze.
3. Improvement of soil fertility and carbon sequestration levels.
4. Increased natural regeneration of trees.
5. More effective nutrient and water cycles.
6. Improvement on animals' health.

Figure 8. Rotational grazing in LH1.

Within this approach, the key principles for soil conservation in El Baldío are as follows:

- Animals don't choose what they eat.
- Animals controlling shrubs.
- Animals activating the carbon pump.
- Animals providing microbiological life to soil.
- Animals fertilizing and seeding.
- Animals respecting the needed recovery time for grasslands and soil fauna.

Results observed

El Baldío implements an exhaustive monitoring system to measure the impact of these interventions in soil health. The monitoring approach covers three main pillars:

- **Biodiversity:** Soil fauna, pollinators, coprophages and decomposition rates
- **Soil functioning:** Chemicals (pH, OM, NPK, Ca...), Soil C, Enzymatic activity, microbial biomass, infiltration rate
- **Pasture health:** Ecological Outcome Verification (EOV), Shrub stratum consumption rate, herbaceous stratum consumption rate.

The effects of rotation grazing have been evaluated in nine plots located on three livestock farms in the southwestern Iberian Peninsula and compared to nine control plots from neighbouring farms under conventional grazing.

The indicators subjected to analysis included: Ecological Health Index (EHI), plant richness and biodiversity, biological activity of ants, earthworms, and butterflies, and soil quality - including bulk density, total carbon and nitrogen, phosphorus, calcium and potassium availability, microbial diversity, and enzymatic activity.

The results reveal better values in all analysed indicators in the plots with adaptive rotation grazing compared to the control ones, except for butterfly biological activity. Significant differences were found in soil coverage, dung decomposition, species richness, and phosphorus and potassium availability ($p < 0.05$). Although more long-term studies are needed, the results show a tendency towards improved ecosystem functioning in the farms using adaptive rotational grazing.

LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil - Saelices el Chico old uranium mine

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte S.L.
LH name	Saelices el Chico Mine area
Region	Salamanca
Country	Spain
Area (Ha)	30ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil and water pollution • Hyperacidification • Hyperoxidation with Fe⁺³ • Hyperconductivity • Hypersulfation • Hyperaluminization • Metallic (Cd, Co, Cu, Mn, Ni, U, Zn) contamination • Non-metallic (As) contamination • Secondary Salinization • Phosphorus deficiency • Extremophile Ecosystems • Bio-catalysis acceleration caused by oxygen-reduction reaction.

LH representative

CVAN, Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte S.L., is a technology-based company specialized in the design, development, and manufacture of "tailor-made" Technosols for different environmental and productive applications. CVAN has extensive experience in waste management and environmental solutions that seek to eliminate or mitigate the problems of contamination in soils and waters derived from various industrial, agricultural, or mining activities. This experience allows CVAN to participate in several R&D&I projects with national or international funding.

CVAN actively collaborates with the Environmental Technology Laboratory of the University of Santiago de Compostela for the execution of its R&D activities and has 5 employees and external collaborations with researchers from the USC.

Geoclimatic description

The uranium mine is located at Saelices el Chico, in the proximities of Ciudad Rodrigo (Salamanca, Spain). The region has Mediterranean-type climatic conditions, with a strong continental influence. The average annual precipitation is 503 mm and temperatures can vary between 4 and 30 °C throughout the year. Soil humidity and temperature regimes are xeric and mesic, respectively.

Figure 9. Geographic location of LH2.

Socioeconomic description

The province of Salamanca is one of the most affected by the risk of depopulation in Spain. Even so, in the year 2022, a significant increase in the number of employed people can be seen in the different sectors, with industry being the only sector to experience a decrease in the number. In the rest of the sectors (agriculture, construction, and services) the trend is positive.

Economic sector ⁴	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Employed people (in thousands)	131,2	130,8	125,0	132,9	136,8
Agriculture	8,1	8,5	8,8	7,1	7,7
Industry	18,1	16,2	14,9	17,7	12,6
Construction	9,0	8,6	6,2	10,0	10,6
Services	96,1	97,6	95,0	98,2	105,9 ⁵

Table 4. Employment percentage per sector LH2 area (Saelices el Chico, Salamanca, Spain).

Until a few years ago, Saelices el Chico (Salamanca, Spain) had an important open-pit uranium mine with an area of 3,2 x 10⁶ m², operated by the state-owned company Empresa Nacional del Uranio S.A. (ENUSA), from 1974 until the end of 2001. After its definitive closure, agriculture and livestock were once again the main sources of economic wealth of the village.

Identified challenges

This mine exploited the most important uranium deposit in Spain, with a reserve of more than 16000 Mg of U₃O₈. The mining and concentration of U was carried out between 1975 and 2000 by the company ENUSA.

After the end of mining activities, a recovery plan was initiated to avoid the risk of radioactivity, which consisted of encapsulating the radioactive waste under a 30 cm thick layer of arkose. A heterogeneous mixture (30 cm thick) of radioactivity-free dump material and rock from the area with its respective soils was deposited on top of this layer.

⁴SEPE 2023 – Informe del Mercado de Trabajo de la provincia de Salamanca – 2022 Data

Lastly, a surface layer (30 cm) of soil from the area that had been removed and accumulated during the mining operation was added. These actions modified, to a greater or lesser extent, the dynamics of the water system, helping to favour surface runoff processes and limiting infiltration to deep layers.

Figure 10. Year 2000. Closure of the uranium mine LH2.

The mine soils are developed on different mixtures of source material and sulphide-rich mining waste. These mixtures of materials diminish the negative effect of the waste dump materials, since the total concentrations of potentially toxic elements are similar to the levels found in natural soils. However, these soils present a high risk, as they generate acidic drainage waters rich in potentially toxic elements and sulphates. In warm weather, evaporation of this acid drainage causes the precipitation of evaporite salts that are temporary sinks for sulphate and metals. The natural soils adjacent to the Fe mine are poor in nutrients and organic matter, which, together with the climatic conditions of the area, leads to low vegetative growth.

Figure 11. Acid drainage in LH2.

Taking into account the limiting conditions of the soils and the corresponding irrigation, it was essential to act, minimizing the oxidation of sulphides and improving fertility. The main objective was to establish vegetation cover and stimulate soil genesis and associated biogeochemical processes, such as nutrient cycling.

Proposed solution

The contaminated soil by uranium mining activities was restored using artificial soils: technosols. Technosols are soils, not mixtures of unstructured materials. After an exhaustive analytical study and thermodynamic modelling of the conditions and limitations of the initial system, these are designed, formulated, and elaborated in the "image of natural soils", taking into account the specific objectives of soil, water and ecosystem remediation, the desired potential uses and the available materials and technologies.

Technosols contain organic and inorganic nanoparticles and microorganisms, within a porous microstructure with high specific surface area and variable and permanent charges. Technosols are designed in a way that prevents contamination and directs the system towards self-sustainable biostatic conditions. These fulfil both the environmental and productive functions of soils while containing fewer contaminants than the receiving system and/or the defined thresholds to prevent harm to health and ecosystem conservation. This ensures that they cannot become sources of pollution. They react and evolve by the same edaphic and biogeochemical processes as the natural soils in their environment, converging with them.

Results observed

6 months after implementing the technosols in Saelices el Chico, significant improvements were observed. The production of grasslands, biodiversity, and carbon sequestration showed positive outcomes. However, the most remarkable change was the transformation of hyperacid surface waters into neutral waters, with reduced levels of metals, metalloids, and sulphates. Additionally, there was an increase in water retention capacity, a reduction in runoff, an extension of the vegetative period, and a shift from resistance to resilience.

Figure 12. Grassland and biodiversity recovery in LH2.

Most values improve positively, with the correction of acidity, the neutralization of the presence of aluminium, copper, cobalt, nickel, zinc, and other metals. In 2020, tests showed there is still high presence of Manganese, the only metal that continues to represent a risk to be overcome. The measures in the soil, the runoffs and the retention ponds showed positive correction values after the intervention with technosols, while the main boil still maintains a high level of acidity, having passed from an extremophiles' environment to the biodiversity of an acid lagoon. In conclusion, the improvements in critical areas are still an ongoing process, while in most of the mines the rate of remediation is particularly high.

Figure 14. 2018. Mine surroundings before intervening with technosols (LH2).

Figure 13. 2020. Mine surroundings after 2 years intervention with technosols (LH2).

LH3. Atlantic Industrial Soil – Old Touro Copper Mine

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte S.L. (CEVAN)
LH name (location)	Touro
Region	Galicia
Country	Spain
Area (Ha)	560 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil and water pollution • Hyperacidification • Hyperoxidation with Fe⁺³ • Hypersulfation • Hyperaluminization • Metallic contamination (Mn, Cu, Zn, Ni) • Extremophile Ecosystems • Bio-catalysis acceleration caused by oxygen-reduction reaction.

LH representative

CVAN, Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte S.L., is a technology-based company specialized in the design, development, and manufacture of "tailor-made" Technosols for different environmental and productive applications. CVAN has extensive experience in waste management and environmental solutions that seek to eliminate or mitigate the problems of contamination in soils and waters derived from various industrial, agricultural, or mining activities. This experience allows CVAN to participate in several R&D&I projects with national or international funding.

CVAN actively collaborates with the Environmental Technology Laboratory of the University of Santiago de Compostela for the execution of its R&D activities and has 5 employees and external collaborations with researchers from the USC.

Geoclimatic description

Touro is a Spanish municipality belonging to the province of A Coruña, in the autonomous community of Galicia. Touro is located south of the province of A Coruña, bordering the river Ulla, which separates it from the municipality of Villa de Cruces (Pontevedra). To the north it borders with the municipality of El Pino; to the east, with Arzúa, and to the west, with Boqueixón.

Touro's climate is clearly defined by the oceanic influence, where temperatures are mild, with an average annual temperature of 12.6°C, an average minimum temperature of 7.9°C and an average maximum temperature of 17.2°C. As for the rainfall regime, the municipality is characterized by abundant rainfall (average annual rainfall = 1.886 mm), distributed mainly in autumn, winter and early spring.

The Touro mine is located in a formation of Precambrian granitic amphibolites mineralized with metallic sulphides, pyrite and pyrrhotite, with significant levels of chalcopyrite and minor amounts of blende and other metallic sulphides. The minerals present in the superficial cover of the deposit are Ferrihydrite, Goethite, Jarosite and Schwermanite (among others), which are accompanied in the summer by different secondary sulphates of Iron, Magnesium, etc. Its origin is similar to that of the so-called "Faja Piritica Andaluza", volcanic sedimentary in the oceanic crust bottoms. But, unlike this one, the content of As, Cd, Hg, Se, Pb and Zn is much lower. The amphibolitic material corresponds to oceanic crust, having dated zircons in similar rocks from Galicia from 900 and 1100 million years ago. On these materials, there is a formation of schistose rocks attributed to the Precambrian-Paleozoic transition.

Figure 15. Geographic location of LH3.

Socioeconomic description

Touro is a relatively small municipality with a population of 3,500 people. Most of its socioeconomic characteristics resemble the situation in other rural municipalities, with a progressive loss of population and a relatively high percentage of the population over 64 years old (35%, while in the region is 25%).

EMPLOYMENT BY SECTOR	% of employment
Primary sector (agriculture)	15%
Industry	19%
Construction	10%
Tertiary sector (services)	56%

Table 5. Employment percentage per sector LH3 area (Touro, Galicia, Spain).

Traditionally, the agricultural and livestock sector was Touro's mainstay of the economy. Nowadays few young people are incorporated directly in this sector, although small parishes with a low density of livestock farms still exist. It is worth mentioning the persistence of the vegetable gardens, as suppliers of food for Galician households but not used to generate wealth directly, the slaughter of pigs and the breeding of chickens, sheep, and rabbits. The opening of an industrial park in the municipality in 2018 also served as a stimulus for its economy and the production of employment in this sector, which today employs almost 20% of all workers living in Touro.

Another important sector was mining. The Rio Tinto mining operations, now closed, provided employment for a short period of time (1974-1986) where more lasting economic activities were not developed. The owners of *Explotaciones Gallegas* have an agreement to try to resume production at the mine with the multinational Atalaya Mining. The first request to the Xunta to reopen the Touro mine was rejected. The company has exhausted the administrative route with several appeals and sued the Xunta in court. The matter is being reviewed by the Superior Court of Justice of Galicia. In any case, the mining alliance has announced that it will present another project for the mine.

Identified challenges

The mine of Touro is located 20 km NE of Santiago de Compostela. It is an ore deposit of metallic sulphides, with an area of 600 ha, that has been exploited by the company Río Tinto Patiño for fourteen years (1974-1988) to extract copper. This activity led to a profound degradation of the environment with deep cuts, vertical walls, sterile dumps, and a large mine tailings pond. The materials left on the surface, lacking vegetation and soil cover, undergo a rapid oxidation of the sulphides generating a hyper-acidic mine drainage which contaminates the rivers of the Ulla basin.

Since the early years of operation, processes of sulphide oxidation were identified, probably due to the rapid oxidative kinetics of pyrrhotite. Excavation and extraction pits, waste rock dumps, and a flotation sludge waste pond, with the latter being the main source of hyperacid waters. The mine soils exhibited hyperacid reactions under forced oxidation conditions, with minimal nutrients and the absence of any biotic activity except for extremophiles. Seeds did not germinate, and any plant that managed to establish itself was quickly eliminated. From the end of mining operations until the start of rehabilitation activities in 1989, the food chain was completely eradicated in the mine soils, and the aquatic fauna of vertebrates and aquatic insects in the surrounding streams were eliminated.

Proposed solution

To accelerate the rehabilitation processes, the kinetics of the main types of soil reactions were analysed, and the fastest ones were selected (ionic associations, ion exchange, and adsorption) to design interventions aiming to neutralize them.

Figure 16. 2004. Before technosols intervention (LH3): pH 2,6-2,8; only extremophile organisms.

Figure 17. 2018. After technosols intervention (LH3): pH 6,5-7,5; entire trophic chain, productivity, and CO₂ fixation.

Rehabilitation activities began in 1989, starting with the incorporation of liming residues (mussel shells and biomass combustion ash) and the planting of pine and eucalyptus trials. The rate of plant elimination was reduced to a small percentage. After studying the Eh-pH conditions and geochemical conditions of the soils, the idea of rehabilitating with technosols. was raised. These were artificial soils made from mixtures of inorganic and organic residues, considering that soils with the appropriate composition and properties could be designed to mitigate the impacts by applying knowledge from Soil Science and Biogeochemistry. The selected materials for the elaboration of technosols included organic reducers to decrease the kinetics of sulphide oxidation, liming agents to neutralize excess acidity, sulphate adsorbents to reduce the mobility of the main mobilizing anion, and nutrients to restore biological activity.

For the design of the soils, natural or anthropogenic soils were used as models (Terra preta and Historical Maori soils). The first soils used as a model were sambaqui soils, elaborated by the Guarani indigenous people inhabiting the mangrove areas of the coast of Sao Paulo (Brazil). These soils have formed in the mangroves of the Cananea area due to the abandonment of oyster shells used for food, which mix with biomass remnants, ashes, and charcoals from cooking fires. In the production of technosols, the oyster shells were replaced with mussel shells (biogenic CaCO_3). The second model used was Andosols, chosen for their ability to adsorb anions and heavy metals and their buffering capacity (Andic technosols). Later, nutrient rich eutrophic technosols were added to enhance fertility and biotic activity, imitating the qualities of Amazonian Terra Preta soils (Practic technosols).

The whole mine has been treated with technosols, except for a 5ha area that has been left untreated as a control area. In the dumps, the Andic technosols, with a high content of labile organic matter, diverse tree plantations were developed: eucalyptus, pines and deciduous, while in the cuttings regular vegetation is also growing. Activities to restore the mine are still ongoing nowadays by the company *Tratamientos Ecológicos Gallegos*, that produces the technosols in their premises located in the mine land.

For the recovery of the quality of hyperacid waters, the construction of a "reactive wetland" began in 2002. A reactive wetland is an artificial wetland with multiple technosols to accelerate biogeochemical reactions:

- Impermeable eutrophic technosol,
- Reducing technosol, neutralizing technosol,
- Sulphate adsorbent technosol,
- Eutrophic technosol.

The goal was to lower the Eh from > 600 mV to < 300 , to reduce sulphates to sulphides and raise the pH, causing the precipitation of aluminium and heavy metals. The development of *Typha latifolia* was encouraged inside the wetland to contribute biodegradable organic matter and maintain at least sub-oxic conditions. A vegetative cover with *Salix atrocinerea* was established at the edges. Starting from 2008, the system became self-sustaining, without new material inputs. A 6-hectare reactive wetland treated leachates from approximately 200 hectares of waste rock dumps and hyper acidic pits.

On the platform of an amphibolite pit, the construction of a reactive wetland began, closing an area with low-permeability eutrophic technosols to collect and contain the hyperacid waters from the elevated waste rock dumps, maintaining an average residence time of 2 months.

Results observed

In the reactive wetland, aquatic insects started to develop as early as 2004, starting with water striders followed by backswimmers and aquatic beetles. Later, carnivorous aquatic insect larvae (odonates) emerged, and by 2008, mayflies appeared, indicating an improvement in water quality sufficient for drinking water purposes and direct discharge into the river. The insects supported the feeding of numerous passerine birds and two species of frogs and toads, while these amphibians allowed the development of colonies of coots, snipes, herons, and other waterbirds. Finally, the food chain was completed with the appearance of raptors such as hawks, harriers, and black kites. By 2008, the pH reached values close to 7.0, sulphate levels decreased to below 2000 mg/l, and the concentration of dissolved aluminium dropped to values below 0.1 mg/l (1000 times less than the concentration of leachates entering the reactive wetland from the waste rock dumps).

Figure 18. Evolution of technosols interventions overtime.

In the dump rehabilitated with eutrophic andic technosols, made to imitate soils with andic properties retains sulphate ions and meta-stabilises large amounts of organic matter ($C > 12\%$) in the surface horizons, has become an excellent sink of carbon, and is quite resistant to mineralisation. Twenty-three years later, the pines planted are timber-yielding and spontaneous autochthonous herbaceous and shrubby plants have grown in their undergrowth. An abundant fauna has developed in the food chain, with rabbits, hares, genets, wild boar and fox, and a multitude of passerines and raptors such as the black kite.

LH4. Continental Urban Soil – Peri-urban soils, Zagreb

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	University of Zagreb
LH name (location)	Peri-urban soils Zagreb
Region	Zagreb
Country	Croatia
Area (ha)	1 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overexploitation • Low biodiversity • Structural deterioration • Low soil quality • Soil compaction • Low soil organic matter content • Soil abandonment • Flood risk

LH representative

The Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zagreb (FAZ) is dedicated to the education of highly qualified experts, development and broadening of professional knowledge in the field of agriculture and related sciences.

Applying the highest academic standards, we enable students to acquire competences based on the newest scientific knowledge, for the benefit of the society.

The Vision of the Faculty of Agriculture is to strategically position itself in Croatian higher education and research area, as well as an internationally recognised and acclaimed research and teaching institution.

Geoclimatic description

Zagreb, with its diverse array of land use and types, experiences significant impacts on soil, the environment, and soil ecosystem services due to land use changes. The selection of the City of Zagreb was motivated by the substantial presence of native forests and agricultural land within its boundaries, making it an attractive place to live. However, over the past few decades, deforestation and cultivation have rapidly increased in these areas, without any monitoring of the resulting changes in the soil system and environment.

Figure 19. Geographic location of LH4.

The Lighthouse site, situated in Šašinovečki Lug, near Sesevete, is approximately 15 km away from the FAZ campus and encompasses 76.2 hectares of agricultural lands.

The four land use types in the Zagreb Lighthouse include:

- *Quercus petraea* and *Robinia pseudo acacia* **Forest** (>200 years).
- Apple **Orchard** (since 2007)
- **Abandoned agricultural land** -Secondary Forest (afforested) (since 1991)
- **Grassland** (since 1996)

Figure 20. Overview of LH4 monitored land.

The dominant soil type in the region is stagnosols, characterized by a silty clay loam texture. These soils have developed on Pleistocene loam and Pliocene clay substrata.

Socioeconomic description

Croatia's economy is largely dependent on the service sector, which comprises about 70% of the total GDP. Zagreb, specifically, is its economic centre, generating 31.4% of the country's GDP; important industries in Zagreb are chemical, pharmaceutical, textile, food and drink processing, manufacturing of electrical machines and devices.

Zagreb is also an important business centre, a transport hub, and an international trade centre, considered the junction of trade between Central and East Europe. The largest

industry in Zagreb is wholesale and retail commerce and motor vehicle and motorcycle repair, accounting for 38.8% of the city's revenue, followed by manufacturing, at 20.6%. Most of Croatia's industrial and service sector is clustered in Zagreb. Other notable industries include information and communication, and electricity and gas supply. Professional, scientific, and technical activities account for just 5% of the city's revenue.

The Lighthouse area has three main economic activities relating on two of the land use types mentioned in the previous section:

- Apple production (Apple Orchard)
- Wood stock (Quercus petraea - Robinia pseudoacacia Forest)

Identified challenges

In Zagreb, 2/3 of the land is in agricultural and forest land, and at least half of its land is used for agriculture. The increasing global demand for natural goods accelerates the conversion of native vegetation into agricultural lands, and this also affect peri-urban and urban soils.

As of today, there are almost no-good practices detected in land use and agricultural practices in Zagreb. So far, all agricultural practices have been carried out with the same methods that have been used for decades, following the practices learned from those who worked the land before them. Because of this, the use of pesticides and mineral fertilizers is still widespread, there is very poor crop rotation or there is no crop rotation at all, no cover cropping, no intermediate cropping etc. In addition, soil health has not been monitored, so no related measures have been taken.

It is also necessary to consider the type of soil in Zagreb, which is dominantly stagnosols, with silty clay loam texture, developed on Pleistocene loam and Pliocene clay substrata.

Having this type of soil means that there are certain types of problems associated with it, something that has not been considered so far for agricultural practices. The challenges identified for the Lighthouse land uses are as follows:

- Soil is very susceptible to compaction.
- Soil is susceptible to erosion.
- Has poor structural stability.

Proposed solution

The lighthouse was created in view of the clear need to monitor both soil health and to develop new agricultural practices in Zagreb, especially considering the amount of soil used for agriculture. This is extremely important from the view of spatial planning since land use generates the ability of soils to increase carbon sequestration or mitigate floods.

The selected soil management practices to address the issues described above were based on promoting appropriate and sustainable natural soil practices for each of the land uses:

QUERCUS PETRAEA AND ROBINIA PSEUDO ACACIA FOREST

- No soil disturbance
- No mineral fertilisation
- Natural decay of trees and leaves

APPLE ORCHARD

- Mulching

- Low soil disturbance
- Permanent grass cover
- Appropriate fertilisation

ABANDONED AGRICULTURAL LAND -SECONDARY FOREST (AFFORESTED)

- No soil disturbance

GRASSLAND

- Mulching
- No soil disturbance
- Permanent vegetation cover

Results observed

To gather data on the soil characteristics, soil sampling is conducted at a depth of 0-10 cm with 8 replicates per land use type, due to Zagreb temperate continental climate, with an average annual precipitation of 852 mm and a mean annual temperature of 10.3 °C.

This sampling is repeated once per season as part of the monitoring strategy. The properties being measured include:

- Bulk density.
- Water holding capacity.
- Soil aggregate stability.
- Mean weight diameter of aggregates, penetration resistance.
- Soil carbon concentration (and stocks).
- CO₂ emissions (fluxes).
- Infiltration.

These parameters provide valuable insights into the physical and chemical attributes of the soil, as well as its capacity to retain water, maintain stable soil aggregates, resist penetration, store carbon, and facilitate CO₂ emissions and infiltration.

Preliminary results showed higher soil water content in grassland than in other land uses. A nearby Cropland land use control area had significantly higher compaction than other land uses, whereas forest land use had lower compaction. Higher compaction was noted during the summer than during other seasons.

The mean weight diameter has the next decreasing trend: orchard > grassland = abandoned agricultural > forest. Mean weight diameter was higher during the winter due to freezing and thawing processes than in other seasons.

Forest land use showed higher water stable aggregates values. Grassland and forest land uses obtained a higher infiltration than abandoned agricultural and orchard.

Soil CO₂ emissions registered higher values during autumn and spring than in winter, and the results show higher CO₂ values in most Lighthouse land uses than in nearby control areas with poor land management approaches.

Finally, CO₂ emissions were higher in grassland than in other land uses. Preliminary results indicate that land uses with intensive agricultural practices decline soil quality and flood retention capacity in peri-urban areas.

LH5. Boreal Urban Soil – Baltupiai urban gardens

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB)
LH name (location)	Baltupiai
Region	Vilnius
Country	Lithuania
Area (Ha)	2.41 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flood risk • Soil erosion • Soil compaction • Soil pollution • Reduced biodiversity • Reduced organic matter

LH representative

Mykolas Romeris
universitetas

The Mykolas Romeris University Laboratories (MRU LAB) is composed of interdisciplinary teams of scientists, researchers, students and other interested individual groups, who implement MRU research programs, develop an ecosystem based on a high-level of knowledge, state-of-the-art technology, collaboration between science, business, and government institutions and society, and network governance.

The MRU LAB is open not only to MRU, but also to scientists, researchers, students from other institutions and business, government institutions, non-governmental organisations partners, with whom innovative solutions to the most important challenges of modern society are sought.

Geoclimatic description

The average annual temperature is +7.2 °C. The coldest month is January (-3.5 °C), and the warmest is July (+17.8 °C) (1971–2000). Vilnius has a population of 588,412 (January 1, 2021) and an area of 401 km². Since 1984, the city's historical centre has been acknowledged as a UNESCO World Heritage Site. According to the Vilnius master plan (Vilnius municipality, 2022), green zones cover an area of 73.52 km² or 18.4 % of the municipal territory.

Figure 21. LH5 location

Socioeconomic description

Vilnius is the major economic centre of Lithuania. The GDP per capita in Vilnius metropolitan area (Vilnius County) is almost 30.000€, making it the wealthiest city in Lithuania and the second-wealthiest city in the Baltic states after Tallinn. The most important sectors of Lithuania's economy in 2020 were wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation, and food services (29.9%), industry (20.5%) and public administration, defence, education, human health, and social work activities (16.1%).

Community of urban gardeners of Baltupiai. Old neighbourhoods inside Vilnius, are mainly composed by individual houses surrounded by gardens. Most of the gardens in Baltupiai were established in late 1950s. The gardens are mainly used for personal and family purposes. Approximately from 2010 many gardeners have stopped planting fruits and vegetables and arranged lawns. The gardeners are not associated in a formal association.

Identified challenges

Community of urban gardeners of Baltupiai. Old neighbourhood in inside Vilnius mainly composed by individual houses surrounded by gardens.

The main issues identified with soil in Baltupiai are the following:

- Soil erosion, compaction and pollution. One of the biggest problems associated to soil use in Baltupiai is that some of the lawns are managed unsustainably. This increases soil degradation (e.g., reduced organic matter and biodiversity)
- Flooding regulation: in the last year, several parks are being flooded, likely due to the unsustainable management.

Proposed solution

Taking into account the specific difficulties encountered with the gardens in Baltupiai, the LH assessed the following ecosystem services to understand the impact of different practices on them:

- Flood regulation
- Erosion regulation
- Food production
- Carbon sequestration
- Recreation

In addition to the sample collection, the LH will carry out the following activities:

- Survey of farmers for ES assessment (cultural).
- Engagement of different stakeholders: municipality, NGO's, farmers, Ministry of the environment and agriculture.
- Proximal Sensing (UAV) analysis to assess ecosystem services.

Results observed

LH partners are currently going through extensive workload and this section will be updated in M18 with the final version of the deliverable.

LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil – Mežole, Latvia

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava", The Forest Research Station
LH name (location)	Mežole
Region	Vidzeme
Country	Latvia
Area (Ha)	9 959.5 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse soil organic matter content • Unbalanced soil nutrient content • Soil acidification • Soil erosion on slopes

LH representative

Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" founded in 1946, is the main centre of forest science in Latvia and leader of scientific ideas in forestry and related research and development in the country. The principal goal of LSFRI "Silava" is, by combining interdisciplinary research and innovative methods, to create knowledge and technology that contribute to sustainability, profitability and competitiveness of forest sector and well-being of society in general.

The institute's research areas include forest ecology and silviculture, forest tree breeding and climate change, forest genetic resources, forest regeneration and establishment, forest phytopathology and mycology, forest entomology, forest operations and bioenergy, wildlife management and forest products processing. "Silava" is responsible for the implementation of National Forest Inventory and National GHG Inventory for LULUCF Sector.

The organisation counts with 44 researchers with a doctoral degree in forestry, biology or other sciences.

Station Latvia is a public agency founded by LSFRI Silava and Latvia University of Life sciences and Technologies. Its purpose is to manage the scientific research forests, to ensure the continuity of research for long-term research sites, to equip and monitor environmental and forest objects. In 2001 Council of Ministers of the Republic of Latvia assigned 28 000 hectares of state-owned forest to long-term research purposes

within forestry sector. Today, 12.5% of this total area is covered by long-term research objects.

Geoclimatic description

In Latvia, the average annual air temperature is +5.9°C. The year's warmest month is July, its average temperature is +17.0°C and average maximum temperature +21.5°C. The coldest months are January and February, when the average temperatures are -4.6 and -4.7°C, and average minimums -7.5 and -7.9°C. So far, the highest observed temperature in Latvia is +36.4°C, the lowest: -43.2°C.

The average annual precipitation in Latvia is 667 mm. The months with most precipitation are July and August, in each of which average rainfall is 78 mm. The least precipitation is in February and March – each of which has on average 33 mm. Annual average relative humidity is 81%. The sun shines on average 1790 hours a year, which is about half of the possible sunshine duration (when the sky is clear).

Throughout the year, the generally prevailing winds are from the south, southwest and west. The highest wind speeds are in November, December, and January (monthly averages of 3.9 to 4.0 m/s). The lowest wind speeds are in July and August (monthly averages of 2.8 m/s). The highest wind speed (10-minute average wind speed value) observed so far is 30 m/s, the strongest gusts are 48 m/s.

LH6 is located in the scientific research forests of Mežole forest region in the central part

Figure 22. Planning regions in Latvia (LH6).

Figure 21. Forest districts in Forest Research Station Latvia property (Mežole district is Nr.2).

of Vidzeme region, northeast of Latvia.

Vidzeme is the largest region in the country, covering 15 245 km² or 24% of its territory. The largest part of the region (currently 56%) is occupied by forests, which has been increasing in recent years. Agricultural land accounts for about 34% of the territory. The region is characterized by low built-up density and a high proportion of natural landscapes with low human influence. Two rivers - Rauza and Sepka - flow through the area. Forest ecosystems are representative for Latvia, the main tree species are Scots pine (19.8%), Norway spruce (46.8%), birch (22.7%), black alder (5.7%) and aspen (3.9%). Areas with forest management restrictions for nature conservation purposes take up 37.1% of Mežole forest region. In the nature reserve "Mežole" (Natura 2000 area), EU habitats 91D0, 7110, 7140, 9010, 9080, 7160 are present.

Socioeconomic description

Population in Vidzeme region was 180 766 or 9.7% of the total population in Latvia in 2022. Gross domestic product (GDP) of Vidzeme region was 6.7% of the total GDP in Latvia in 2020, constituting 2 041 935 thousand euro or 11 068 euro per capita. The primary sectors (agriculture, forestry, fisheries) are 14.4% of the Vidzeme region's economic structure. The

most economically active units (the largest number of enterprises) in the region are forestry, woodworking, agriculture, and animal husbandry. According to the Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia (CSB) the employment rate in the region in 2022 in the 15-74 age group was 62.3%, while the unemployment rate was 6.0%. The employment rate in the 15-64 age group was 70.2%, while the unemployment rate was 6.3%. The average salary in Latvia after taxes in 2022 was 1006 EUR while in the Vidzeme region it was 810 EUR per month.^{6 7}

Value added at current prices by economic activities (in 2020) in Vidzeme region (Latvia) ⁸	Vidzeme region	
	Thousand euro	Share from total in Latvia, %
Total	1781927	6.7
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing	255651	19.5
Industry	416533	9.8
Construction	107919	6.4
Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, transportation and storage, accommodation and food service activities, information, and communication	324319	4.3
Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities, professional, scientific, and technical activities, administrative and support service activities	272826	4.5
Public administration and defence, compulsory social security, education, human health and social work activities, arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities, activities of households as employers	404679	7.4

Table 6. Economic added value by sector in LH6 area (Mežole, Vidzeme, Latvia).

Identified challenges

Forest management in boreal/hemi-boreal regions must often face several challenges related to soil quality. Firstly, the threat to soil quality is related to the loss of nutrients due to tree biomass harvesting (i.e., whole tree harvesting including tops and branches), which alter and may cause a disbalance in the availability of nutrients for subsequent tree rotations. Secondly, unsuitable soil preparation methods on slopes may enhance wind and water erosion and the movement of organic matter towards lowland parts. Thirdly, the area contains a former gravel mining site with degraded poor sandy soil, that is necessarily subject to recultivation.

Proposed solution

To prevent insufficient supply of nutrients due to forest harvesting and repeated removal of nutrients by tree biomass, forest fertilization experiments using wood ash and N containing mineral fertilizers were initiated in 2016/2017 in spruce, pine and birch stands.

⁶ <https://stat.gov.lv/en/statistics-themes/environment/nature-resources/tables/drt011-total-and-land-area-regions-cities>

⁷ https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START_EMP_NBB_NBA/NBA031

https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START_EMP_DS_DSV/DSV041/

⁸ <https://stat.gov.lv/en/statistics-themes/economy/national-accounts/2352-gross-domestic-product-regions>

Soil fertilization impacts on groundwater quality and tree radial increment are regularly monitored.

Figure 23. Soil fertilization testing in LH6.

To test approaches for reduction of soil erosion and GHG emissions, tests of diverse soil preparation methods on slopes and lowland parts (disk trenching and mounding) were initiated in 2020. In sites with wet organic soils, soil-to-atmosphere GHG fluxes are being regularly monitored.

Figure 24. Diverse approaches to soil preparation methods in LH6.

LH6 includes former gravel mining area to be recultivated by natural and anthropogenically promoted afforestation. It will increase soil organic matter and nutrient content, improve biodiversity, and preserve already spontaneously established recreation opportunities (off-road motorcycling).

Figure 25. natural and anthropogenic afforestation and recreation area to be recultivated in LH6.

Results observed

The results observed in the LH include the following aspects of soil quality improvement: Return of nutrients removed by tree harvesting via fertilizer, enhanced radial growth of main stand, high increments of the second storey and the undergrowth.

Figure 26. Improved nutrient fixation and tree density in LH6.

Improved regeneration conditions for trees of the young stand, balance GHG emissions.

Figure 27. Improved trees regeneration conditions and GHG emissions in LH6.

Recultivation of degraded area, restoration of productive functions of forest ecosystem, enhancement of above-ground and below-ground biodiversity of flora and fauna, preservation of spontaneously emerged recreation function.

Figure 28. Restoration of forest productive functions through recultivation in LH6.

LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Ekoboerderij de Lingehof (EKO)
LH name (location)	Implementation of regenerative practices for soil health and the protein transition in the Netherlands.
Region	Betuwe / the Netherlands
Country	Netherlands
Area (Ha)	130 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop rotations with legumes • Carbon farming • Alternative fertilisation enhancing balanced soil ecosystems (Bokashi, compost tea, ferments)

Living Lab representative

Ekoboerderij de Lingehof (EKO) is a biodynamic arable farm growing healthy plant-based food with an eye for people and nature. There is a great diversity of crops which are harvested in one go, and then stored or delivered directly to the customer. EKO combines the care for soil fertility with the use of technology and precision agriculture for balanced plant growth and efficient business operations. The farm is keen into trying new approaches or giving others the space for entrepreneurship. EKO pioneers with the biodynamic cultivation of new crops such as quinoa, and white lupine or with companion crops.

Geoclimatic context

Ekoboerderij de Lingehof is based in the Betuwe region (Batavia), this is a historical and geographical region in the Netherlands. A defining feature in the Betuwe is the river landscape in the lowlands of the central Netherlands. It is formed by the Waal, the Lower Rhine, the Lek, the Linge, the Korne and the Zoel.

The landscape in the region consists mainly of an alternation of old stream channels, the stream ridges on either side of them and the bowls of river clay that are further away from the rivers. The old river courses are recognizable in various places in the Betuwse landscape (both inside and outside dikes). Other typical landforms relatively common in the region are river beaches, crevasse channels, embankments, and gullies.

Ekoboerderij de Linge Hof is located on fertile river-clay. This is a typical type of soil in the Betuwe region, characterised by a heavy texture and high fertility, which makes it an ideal soil for horticultural crops as well as orchards and tree nurseries. In particular, the stream ridges, with sandy material on the surface, have traditionally been used for horticulture and are considered one of the best agricultural lands in the Netherlands. River clay has a high-water holding capacity, but it is also very susceptible to compaction when wet and it is very hard to work with when dry, this brings in many challenges when working with agricultural machinery.

Socioeconomic context

The upcoming table presents data pertaining to economic activity in the Netherlands⁹ for the year 2021:

ECONOMIC ACTIVITY	Region GDP %
Agriculture, farming, fishing	2%
Industry	12%
Services	78%
Other	8%

Table 7. The Netherlands GDP data by sector in 2021. Source: CBS 2021.

The Betuwe is best known for its large-scale horticulture, including the fruit cultivation of crops from the rose family; Especially apples, pears, cherries, plums, and strawberries are grown.

The largest cooperative fruit auction in the Netherlands, FruitMasters, is located in Geldermalsen (West Betuwe). To a lesser extent, vineyards also occur in the Betuwe, including the Betuws wine estate, which is one of the largest and most famous vineyards in the Netherlands.

In addition to fruit cultivation in orchards, there are also other branches of horticulture in the region that are relatively common, including greenhouse horticulture (especially in the Over-Betuwe) and tree cultivation.

Pilot whales were also relatively common along the banks of the Betuws; these are still present especially in the Tielerswaard. From the willows harvested from the pilot whales, a specific type of Betuwse basket was traditionally braided, which is called a fowl oak. Fowls are used when harvesting the cherries in June and/or July.

The current main economic activity of the Lighthouse develops around biodynamic and regenerative agriculture with a specific focus on crop sales, innovation projects, education activities and specialised hired labour. The main crops harvested are currently onion, pumpkin, potato, grass-clover, lupin, peas, sugar-maize, wheat, and rye.

Identified challenges

The main issues that EKO wants to solve in the future are the following:

- Difficulties in introducing/ keeping N-fixing crops within the crop rotation due to the absence of value chains that support farmers in getting a good price for their product.
- Reduced availability of good quality organic manure.

⁹ CBS - Statistics Netherlands 2021 - [CBS - Statistics Netherlands](#)

- Water related issues. Disruption of soil structure due to compaction when the soil is wet. Increased incidence of draught events resulting in the need to irrigate more often.
- Biodiversity loss due to the use of chemicals in agriculture.

Proposed solution

In the past years EKO has been experimenting and innovating with the following practices:

- Organic (biodynamic) farming.
- Wide crop rotation (8-13 crops).
- Inclusion of N-fixers in the crop rotation.
- Reduced tillage.
- Diversified green manures.
- Precision agriculture.

The Lighthouse aims to keep innovating further in the direction of regenerative farming, working on soil biology to increase plant health and reduce inputs. Practices that are currently being tested are the following:

- Minimize the time in which the soil is bare, for instance by under-sowing crops with a companion mix that stays on the field after the harvest of the main crops.
- Alternative fertilization by utilizing plant ferments, compost tea and bokashi to increase the crop capacity to access nutrients, therefore increasing nutrient use efficiency. The principle behind this is that by creating a balanced soil ecosystem the plant has a wide variety of symbiotic micro-organisms that can support it with accessing the needed resources.
- (Further) developing business cases around N-fixing crops.

Results observed

Ekoboerderij de Lingehof does not have a standardized monitoring and evaluation methodology as its choices and activities develop 'organically' overtime. Assessment methods are usually empiric and based on day-to-day tasks.

The practices applied in the past by EKO has resulted in a tremendous reduction in the need for (organic) manure input (from 170 to about 70 kg/N ha on average. The overall soil quality at the farm has also improved, we can assess this visually every time we dig in the soil and see a large amount of rainworms and a 'crumbly' soil structure in the soil in most plots. This is also visible in the soil tests.

NOTE

Ekoboerderij de Lingehof currently represents a Lighthouse and will potentially become a Living Lab during the course of the InBestSoil project.

LL 1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil - Grande Pianura del Campidano, la Nurra, la Gallura and other areas of Sardegna

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	Agricultural research agency of Sardinia (AGRIS) – Euro Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change Foundation (CMCC)
LH name (location)	Campidano and other areas
Region	Sardinia
Country	Italy
Area (Ha)	20 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental conditions - Climate change and polluted soils in some areas • Land abandonment - Low profitability of agricultural activities • Soil fertility reduction • Water scarcity & extreme events

LL CHARACTERISTICS

Year of establishment	In process of establishment
Nr of Lighthouses	2
Nr of LL experimental sites	9

LL Representatives

The Euro Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change Foundation

(CMCC)'s mission is to investigate and model the climate system and its interactions with society to provide reliable, rigorous, and timely scientific results as well as foresights and quantitative analysis of our future planet and society which will, in turn, stimulate sustainable growth, protect the environment, and develop science-driven adaptation and mitigation policies in a changing climate.

CMCC collaborates with experienced scientists, economists, and technicians, which work together to provide complete analyses of climate impacts on various systems such as, but not limited to, agriculture, ecosystems, coasts, water resources, health, and economics.

CMCC also supports policymakers in setting and assessing costs, mitigation, and adaptation policies.

Agris

Agencia pro sa chirca in agricoltura
 Agenzia regionale per la ricerca in agricoltura

The Regional Agricultural Research Agency of Sardinia (Agris Sardegna) was established in 2006 by merging five former regional institutions dealing with different aspects of agriculture research and development. The mission of the Agency is to: foster sustainable rural development; protect and enhance animal, plant and microbial biodiversity; develop the agricultural, agro-industrial, forest and fishery sectors. Agris is involved in different activities to achieve its aims, such as research and development projects; technical and scientific advice to farmers, agri-food industries, policymakers and PDO products consortiums; training and dissemination.

Geoclimatic context

Sardinia is the second biggest island in the Mediterranean Sea with an area of 24,100 km². The climate of the Island is Mediterranean, with average annual precipitations ranging from 400 to 1100 mm, mainly distributed in winter and autumn with erratic heavy rainfall in spring and snowfalls in the highlands. The average temperature is between 12 and 18 °C, with mild winters and hot summers (SRACC, 2019¹⁰).

Socioeconomic context

Sardinia's GDP per inhabitant is 70% of the European Union average. At a national level, it ranks among the best regions in the centre-south, but the gap with the high-income northern Italian regions remains unchanged (CRENoS, 2023)¹¹. The provinces of Cagliari and Sassari show the most significant rate of economic development with a good development of the industrial sector¹². The high cost of transportation of goods and electricity, two times as much as that of the Continental Italian Regions and three times as much as that of the EU average, is the primary constraint for the Sardinian economy. In contrast, Tourism and Agri-Food sectors are two lively and vital sources of income for the Island, with sizeable room for growth. Sardinia is the only Italian region that produces a surplus of electricity and exports electricity to Corsica and the Italian mainland¹³.

The main sectors of the Sardinian Economy are as follows:

Sectors ¹⁴	Share of the total	
	Sardinia (% values)	Italy (% values)
Agriculture, farming, fishing	4,1	2,2
Industry	8,7	20,1
Constructions	5,3	5,0
Commerce, hotels and restaurants, transport, services and (tele) communications	81,9	72,7

Table 8. Value added by sectors of economic activity: annual change and share, year 2021 (percentage values) LL1.

Employment by sector is broken down into the following percentages as reported in the following table:

¹⁰ <https://portal.sardegناسira.it/strategia-regionale-di-adattamento>

¹¹ <https://crenos.unica.it/crenosterritorio/sites/default/files/allegati-pubblicazioni-tes/Volume%20versione%20integrale.pdf>

¹² <https://www.infocamere.it/movimprese>

¹³ <https://www.istat.it/>

¹⁴ CRENoS (2023) elaborations on Istat data - Regional economic accounts -

<https://crenos.unica.it/crenosterritorio/sites/default/files/allegati-pubblicazioni-tes/Volume%20versione%20integrale.pdf>

Sectors ¹⁵	Share of the total			
	Sardinia values)	(%)	Italy values)	(%)
Agriculture, farming, fishing		5,5		3,8
Industry		10,1		20,2
Constructions		7,9		6,7
Commerce, hotels and restaurants, transport, services and (tele) communications		76,5		69,4
Total		100		100

Table 9. Employed (aged 15-89) by sector of economic activity, year 2022 (percentage values) LL1.

The economy of Sardinia Island is facing challenges due to its stagnant status, characterized by a high prevalence of small and microeconomic activities, and notable unemployment rates, especially among young people. Furthermore, the economic structure is dominated by the primary sector and an oversized services sector, with the public administration sector holding significant influence (Moro et al. 2016)¹⁶.

Sardinian soils

47.9% of the surface of Sardinia, largely mountainous and hilly, is exploited for 60% for permanent meadows and pastures, 34% for arable land, while agricultural woody crops cover the remaining 6%.

In Sardinia live 3 million sheep, which makes the Island one of the areas of the world with the highest sheep density along with some areas of England and Wales. Sardinia has a multi-millennial tradition in sheep breeding and agriculture.

Agriculture has played a very important role in the economic history of the island, especially in the great Campidano plain, particularly suitable for extensive cereal-legume systems as well as other extensive crops such as forages. Sardinian soils show great variability due to the ancient geological origin, with small and sometimes brackish aquifers, and very small natural water reserves. The scarcity of water was the first problem that was faced for the modernization of the sector, with the construction of a large system of damming of waterways that today reaches almost 2 billion cubic¹⁷ meters of water storage capacity in reservoirs.

Sardinian agriculture is predominantly extensive, with some specialized productions such as wine, olive and artichoke. The 60% of the Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) is occupied by permanent meadows and pastures. Arable land occupies 34.1%, agricultural woody crops 5.7%, and vegetables with only 0.1%. Within the arable land, forage crops account for about 50% of the UAA. Among cereals, durum wheat plays a dominant role. Other main winter cereals are barley and, to a lesser extent, oats. In the province of Oristano there is an important rice growing area. Maize growing areas are also scattered over several areas of Sardinia where animal husbandry plays an important role. There are also horticultural crops such as artichoke and tomato, particularly in the province of Oristano. Among tree crops grapevine, olive and citrus play a dominant role (SRACC, 2019)¹⁸.

¹⁵ CRENoS (2023) elaborations on Istat data - Rilevazione sulle forze di lavoro

¹⁶ Moro, D., Sideri, M., & Usai, S. (2019). L'economia della Sardegna. Una competitività fragile. In *Sardegna. Geografie di un'isola* (pp. 215-227). Franco Angeli.

¹⁷ https://autoritadibacino.regione.sardegna.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/2023_03_15_dCI_04_allegato_B.pdf

¹⁸ <https://portal.sardegna-sira.it/strategia-regionale-di-adattamento>

Sardinia is the Italian region with the largest forest extension, with almost half of the Island covered by forested areas, mainly composed by Mediterranean maquis (Cipolla and Montaldo, 2022)¹⁹. In particular, Cork oak forest represents an important essential component of the Mediterranean landscape, providing about 80% of Italian cork (Seddaiu et al, 2020)²⁰. Sardinia also shows a rich biodiversity in flora and fauna, with a great deal of endemism.

In Sardinia, the soil is uniquely fragile due to the island's landscape morphology and climate, making it acutely sensitive to degradation if land use changes don't sufficiently consider its inherent qualities and limitations (Vacca et al., 2002)²¹.

Cereals

Olive

Vineyard

Orange

Figure 29. Typical Mediterranean crops LL1.

Soil degradation is a significant issue caused by various factors, particularly anthropogenic factors. These include the removal of Mediterranean maquis, uncontrolled wildfires, overusing water resources, and abandoning traditional land management practices. Intensive farming practices can also lead to soil degradation (Zucca et al., 2010)²².

The actions taken in the past have resulted in significant land degradation, endangering about 50% of Sardinia's land. If not addressed effectively, this could lead to irreversible degradation. (Motroni)²³. From 2006 to 2021, the data indicates that land consumption in Sardinia has increased in absolute terms and per capita. The rise in the latter can be attributed to a decline in the resident population in the region, which suggests a less efficient use of land resources over time. When examining the provincial differences, it's notable that Cagliari, the province with the most significant increase in land consumption, also saw a parallel growth in per capita consumption (CRENoS, 2023)²⁴.

Lighthouse of the LL1: Sardinian Conservation Agriculture Long Term Experiments (LTE)

The Sardinian Living Lab is made up of 9 experimental sites and 2 Lighthouses. See more details in the sections below.

¹⁹ Cipolla and Montaldo, 2022. <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/14/19/4893>

²⁰ Seddaiu et al, 2020 <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4907/11/9/971>

²¹ Vacca A., Loddo S., Serra G., Aru A. Soil degradation in Sardinia (Italy): main factors and processes. In : Zdruli P. (ed.), Steduto P. (ed.), Kapur S. (ed.). 7. International meeting on Soils with Mediterranean Type of Climate (selected papers). Bari: CIHEAM, 2002. p. 413-423. (Options Méditerranéennes: Série A. Séminaires Méditerranéens; n. 50). 7. International Meeting on: Soils with Mediterranean Type of Climate, 2001/09/23-28, Valenzano (Italy). <http://om.ciheam.org/om/pdf/a50/04002055.pdf>

²² Zucca, C., Canu, A., & Previtali, F. (2010). Soil degradation by land use change in an agropastoral area in Sardinia (Italy). *Catena*, 83(1), 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2010.07.003>

²³ Motroni

²⁴ <https://crenos.unica.it/crenosterritorio/sites/default/files/allegati-pubblicazioni/Volume%20versione%20integrale.pdf>

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The core of the lighthouses of LL1 is a Long-Term experiment (LTE), including two sites (Ussana and Benatzu) that are only 1 km apart. It is a 20-year experiment started in 2003. Therefore, the sites share the same climate but have very different soil conditions due to the ancient pedological origin of the area. The current cropping system is conservation agriculture, applied to improve sustainability and soil fertility and soil health. The experimental design follows a split-plot design with three complete randomized blocks, allowing for systematic and controlled testing of conservation agriculture practices.

Figure 30. Distribution of LHs within LL1.

LH	Location	Soil type	Fertility	Temp.	Precipitation	Main economic activities	Main crops
Ussana	39.410 N, 9.091 E, 94 m a.s.l.	Petrocalcic Palexeralf soil	Medium/ medium- low	Min: 10.8 °C Max: 23.2 °C	464 mm	Durum wheat production for semolina Bread- and pasta- making	Durum wheat, Faba bean Proteic field pea
Benatzu	39.420 N, 9.086 E, 89 m a.s.l.	Vertic Epiaquept soil	Medium- high/ high	Min: 10.8 °C Max: 23.2 °C	464 mm		

Table 10. Main characteristics of the LHs within LL1.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

- Environmental conditions: worsened by climate change and polluted soils.
- Land abandonment due to low profitability of agricultural activities.
- Soil fertility reduction (common to other Mediterranean areas).
- Water scarcity & extreme events: Reduced sustainability of rainfed extensive crops such as cereals, forages etc. and animal husbandry such as breeding sheep in hilly areas etc.

INTERVENTIONS

The experimental design split the plots into 3 randomized blocks where the following interventions were applied:

MAIN PLOTS (2400 m²): Three tillage methods were implemented:

- No tillage or Sod Seeding (SS)
- Minimum or Reduced Tillage (RT)
- Conventional Tillage (CT)

These interventions were compared with conventional tillage practices.

SUB-PLOTS (600 m²): Crop rotations methods were applied:

- Single cropping with durum wheat (CW - Continuous Wheat)
- Durum wheat/legume crop rotation (LW - Legumes/Wheat)

From 2015, changes in rotation treatments were implemented due to phytopathology problems caused by accumulation of nematodes (Foxi et al, 2017) especially with Continuous Wheat (CW) and Conventional Tillage methods.

Therefore, CW was replaced by two new rotations treatments:

- Durum wheat/faba bean rotation (FW – faba bean/wheat)
- Durum wheat/field pea rotation (PW – field pea/wheat).

These crop rotation practices allow for the evaluation of different cropping strategies and their impact on soil health, nutrient cycling, and overall agricultural productivity within the context of Conservation Agriculture.

DATA COLLECTED

In the last **20 years numerous data have been collected**, mainly:

- **Crop** data
 - durum wheat: grain yield and quality (moisture, protein, gluten, gluten index, 1000 kernel weight (TKW), specific weight.
 - Faba bean: grain yield, grain moisture and TKW.
 - Field pea: grain yield, grain moisture and TKW.
- **Soil** data: soil profiles since 2003, soil texture and chemical analysis for 2-3 layers (every 4-5 years), compaction curve.
- **Crop management** data.
- **Meteorological and Climate** data: daily Tmin, Tmax, Prec, Solar radiation from locally placed field weather stations.

In addition to chemical aspects, the following data was also collected:

- Soil organic matter (SOM) in CW and LW
- Penetration resistance
- Presence of Pathogens

RESULTS

After implementing Conservation Agriculture Practices for 10 years, the following main results were observed:

- No difference in crop yield on durum wheat
- Increase of soil organic carbon in the medium-long term period
- Mitigation of GHG emissions due to a reduction of the use of fossil fuels as well as an increase of soil organic carbon
- Reduction of phytopathology problems (nematodes) especially with continuous wheat and conventional tillage methods based on mouldboard plough.

Experimental Sites of the LL1

The Living Lab 1 is under development and will include several farms in the Campidano plain area and in the North of Sardinia region. A total of 9 experimental sites will be set up: 7 sites are related to cereal cultivation, 1 to olive trees and 1 to vineyard. The table below collects information on the different experimental sites, treatment and planned sampling campaigns.

The sites and the sampling design may be subject to changes depending on the development of the project and the criteria established with the coordinators of the involved WPs:

Municipality	ID	Crop	Treatment (Tillage)	Sample year 2023	Sample year 2025
Sanluri	SS1	Durum wheat	Sod seeding	x	
	RT2	Durum wheat	Reduced tillage	x	
	CT3	Durum wheat	Conventional tillage	x	x
Samatzai	SS4	Durum wheat	Sod seeding	x	
	RT5	Durum wheat	Reduced tillage	x	
	CT6	Durum wheat	Conventional tillage	x	x
Guspini	SS7	Durum wheat	Sod seeding	x	
Capoterra	ORG8	Vineyard	Organic (plus grassing)	x	x
Sorso	RT9	Olive	Organic (No tillage & shredding)	x	x

Table 11. Experimental sites characteristics in LL1.

Living Lab focus area: Conservation agriculture

The Living Lab in Sardinia focuses on Conservation Agriculture (CA) and sustainable crop management over cereals, olives and vineyards, and tests CA techniques based on the learnings from the existing Lighthouses in the sites selected.

Conservation Agriculture is based on three pillars aiming at:

- Minimizing or avoiding soil disturbance through reduced tillage and sod seeding.
- Maintaining permanent soil cover through residue management and cover crops.
- Promoting plant diversity through crop rotation.

Figure 31. LL1 process for conservation agriculture.

These practices aim to preserve soil health, prevent erosion, and enhance sustainability in agriculture. Conservation agriculture offers several advantages, including:

REDUCED EROSION	MITIGATES GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS
IMPROVED SOIL STRUCTURE, ORGANIC MATTER CONTENT, AND FERTILITY	STABILIZES YIELDS
CONSERVATION OF SOIL WATER CONTENT	HELPS MAINTAINING CULTIVATION IN DISADVANTAGED RURAL AREAS
REDUCES CULTIVATION COSTS,	ENHANCED SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES

Table 12. Advantages of conservation agriculture in LL1.

These benefits contribute to the preservation of soil health, environmental sustainability, and the long-term viability of agricultural systems.

LL1 Challenges to be addressed

The main challenges to be addressed both in the LHs and LL1 are:

- Environmental conditions: worsened by climate change and polluted soils.
- Land abandonment due to low profitability of agricultural activities.
- Soil fertility reduction (common to other Mediterranean areas).
- Water scarcity & extreme events: Reduced sustainability of rainfed extensive crops such as cereals, forages etc. and animal husbandry such as breeding sheep in hilly areas etc.

Potential Activities

- Test benefits from new soil management strategies implemented in two experimental sites.
- Evaluate the sustainable soil management strategies of the farms already applying such strategies to demonstrate to other farmers the advantage of applying them from a physical, ecological, and economic point of view.
- Raising farmers' awareness of soil health issues.
- Informing farmers about the potential long-term benefits of applying conservation agriculture for the soil health and the sustainability of this management.
- Exchange of experiences between farmers practising conservation agriculture and those still practising conventional tillage based on ploughing through technical meetings and open field days.

Monitoring & Impact

The LTE Lighthouses will be used as a solution demonstration, training, and communication to farmers example within the Lighthouse. These serve as a platform to showcase innovative solutions, provide training programs, and facilitate effective communication channels for farmers, fostering knowledge exchange and the adoption of sustainable practices in agriculture.

Special attention will be dedicated to ensuring the engagement and participation of the different stakeholders of the LL. More specifically, periodic meetings are planned with the farmers to constantly guide them in the implementation/evaluation of sustainable soil practices. Farmers will be supported in each phase of the project's activities in order to enhance farmers' motivation, build trust in sustainable soil management practices, and strengthen the collaboration between farmers, academia, and policymakers. The goal is to give impulse for a permanent LL for agriculture Mediterranean soils as a meeting point for sharing experience, training, improving capacity building, discuss, and for being more incisive in the market.

LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil - Climate protection through humus build-up, Baselland Canton, Switzerland

General Information

LH Coordinator partner	The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)
LH name	Climate protection through humus build-up
Region	Cantons of Basel
Country	Switzerland
Area (Ha)	1100 Ha
Soil health challenges	Reduced organic inputs, strong temperature increase

LL CHARACTERISTICS

Year of establishment	2019
Nr of Lighthouses	2 (selected out of 10)
Nr of LL experimental sites	10 (selected out of 55)

Living Lab representative

FiBL The Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL is one of the world's leading institutes in the field of organic agriculture. Its locations are situated in Switzerland, Germany, Austria, Hungary (ÖMKi), France and a representation in Brussels (Belgium) through FiBL Europe. FiBL's strengths lie in its interdisciplinary research, innovations developed jointly with farmers and the food industry, solution-oriented development projects and rapid knowledge transfer from research into practice. FiBL is a member of the ENOLL network since 2021.

In the context of InBestSoil project, FiBL will focus on evaluating the impact of carbon farming initiatives and testing new interventions through the Baselland Canton Living Lab in Switzerland.

Geoclimatic context

The canton of Basel-Landschaft, with an area of 51.800 ha, is located in the northwestern part of Switzerland. Basel-Binningen (47.54 N / 7.58 E) and Rünenberg (47.43 N / 7.88 E) show an annual mean temperature of 10.5 °C and 9 °C. The annual precipitation is 842 mm and 1.009 mm, respectively (Bundesamt für Meteorologie und Klimatologie MeteoSchweiz, 2021, 2020).

Figure 32. LL2 location map

Socioeconomic context

LL2 is situated in the economic region of Basel that includes parts of France and Germany as well. Since the 1960s there are agreements in force to strengthen contacts within the so-called Regio Basiliensis. This economic co-operation is often considered the most intensive in Europe.

From the 17th century until the beginning of the 20th century silk weaving was important in the region. Factories were established as early as 1850, following the finding of salt in underground deposits, founding industries such as the chemical industry. Today, the economic region of Basel is considered the second largest economic centre in Switzerland, after Zurich. The chemical industry and the pharmaceutical industry are of greatest significance in the canton. There are a number of multinationals in the city of Basel, attracting workers from both cantons of Basel and the areas across the border in France and Germany. Banking and finance are important as is the service sector in general. Small and middle-sized businesses employ a significant number of people, both in the city as the two municipalities. The canton is also known for its banking sector, and for being the worldwide seat of the Bank for International Settlements.

Agriculture in the canton includes fruit growing, dairy farming and cattle breeding, but is of minor importance for the GDP.

Soils in canton Basel-City and Basel-Country

About 41% (21,423 ha) of soil in the canton of Basel-Landschaft is agricultural land, of which 54 % is grassland, 43 % is arable land and 3 % is special cultivated land²⁵.

The geology is dominated by three tectonic units that formed during the Tertiary: The Upper Rhine Graben, the Tafeljura and the Faltenjura. The Tafeljura and Faltenjura consist of solid limestone, marl, and clay sediments of the Mesozoic era. The Upper Rhine Graben was filled with deposits of continental and marine sediments formed by calcareous sandstones, conglomerates, marls, and clays (Amt für Umweltschutz und Energie). Aeolian sediments (mainly silt, often clayish and calcareous) were deposited since the middle Pleistocene, forming loess layers of up to 17 m thickness in the western part of the canton of Basel-Landschaft^{26 27}. In the same period, glacial- and fluvial transport led to deposits of gravel and sand to silty material in valleys, whereby fluvial processes occur until today and form the alluvions (Bitterli-Brunner, 1988). Dominant soil types in the region are Eutric and Calcaric

Figure 33. Structure of LL2

²⁵ Statistisches Amt des Kantons Basel-Landschaft, 2022.

²⁶ Lander et al., 2017

²⁷ Zollinger, 1991

Cambisols, Haplic Luvisols, and Stagnic Cambisols²⁸. The altitude rises from north to south, from 245 to 1,150 m.a.s.l.

LL2 Structure

Since January 2021, the Ebenrain Center for Agriculture, Nature, and Food (Ebenrain) has been implementing the project "Climate protection through humus build-up", in collaboration with Bio-Nordwestschweiz and the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) in Frick. Together, the partners are pursuing two major goals:

1. To make agricultural soils more adaptable to drought and thus more resilient to climate extremes by building up humus.
2. To store CO₂ from the atmosphere in agricultural soils.

The aim is to increase the humus content over 6 years on 55 farms with a total project area of 1100 ha in the cantons of Basel-Landschaft and Basel-Stadt. The project is scientifically accompanied by FiBL and an advisory group with representatives from the Basel Farmers' Association (BVBB), farmers and Ebenrain experts is supporting the project.

A cantonal bank (Basellandschaftliche Kantonbank) offers the opportunity to support the project through a regional compensation mechanism. In this way, BLKB would like to compensate 1000 tons of greenhouse gas emissions in regional agriculture.

Key actions on the participating farms are:

- Three farm-specific consultations during the project period. During the first visit a farm-specific SOM build up plan is developed to be conducted during the whole project duration.
- Analytical measurements of the humus content in the 1st, 3rd, and 6th year.
- An impact-oriented compensation of the carbon sequestration.

Out of the 55 participating farms 10 have been selected for the InBestSoil project interventions and in-depth sampling campaigns.

Living Lab focus area.

The aim of LL2 is to adapt agriculture to climate change in order to strengthen soil resilience and soil fertility to climate extreme events, and also, to provide food security in the future. For this purpose, farmers were advised to increase the humus content of the soil, which also impacts soil fertility and carbon sequestration capacity; to ensure farmer participation, compensation payments were created.

Lighthouse of the LL2

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The DOK field experiment is a long-term farming system comparison trial, located in Therwil, Canton of Basel Landschaft, Switzerland (7°32' E, 47°30' N), which started in 1978. The soil type is a Haplic Luvisol²⁹, developed on deep deposits of alluvial loess. The mean annual temperature is 10.5 °C (1.5 °C increase since 1978) with a mean annual precipitation of 840 mm³⁰.

²⁸ IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022.

²⁹ WRB, 2015

³⁰ Krause et al., 2020.

This trial investigates the differences between the biodynamic (BIODYN), organic-biological (BIOORG) and conventional (CONFYM) agricultural systems since 1978. The trial simulates farms with mixed crop and livestock production. The exclusively mineral-fertilised, conventional system (CONMIN) stands for livestock-free agriculture. In the BIODYN, BIOORG and CONFYM systems, manure and slurry are applied according to two livestock densities.

The research results on arable farming, soil fertility, nutrient supply, biodiversity, and climate relate to five different crops that are currently grown alternately as part of the seven-year crop rotation: Silage maize, soybeans, winter wheat, potatoes, and clover grass. The results of 42 years of research have been published in scientific journals and are also of great interest for agricultural practice.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

The DOK trial is designed as a system comparison trial considering mainly different fertilisation and pest control strategies, which reflects the general trend in shifting food systems and changing climatic conditions.

INTERVENTIONS

In the DOK trial, two organic and two conventional farming systems are compared with an unfertilized control³¹. They have the same crop rotation within seven-year crop rotation periods (CRP) with two years of grass-clover ley (Supplementary Table S1) but receive different types of fertilisers. Each farming system is replicated four times (columns), and the crop rotation is running temporally shifted in three subplots. This sums up to 96 parcels (5 × 20 m each), arranged in a randomized split-block design. All farming systems have the same type and frequency of tillage but receive different types of plant protection.

DATA COLLECTED

In the DOK trial fundamental agronomical, ecological, and economical parameters are assessed on a regular, at least annual basis since 1978. In addition, all sampled materials are archived and available for additional experiments. Measuring and sampling campaigns for more specific scientific questions are conducted continuously.

RESULTS

During the 42-year field experiment, organic systems used 92% less pesticides and 76% less available nitrogen than conventional systems in an arable rotation. Measurements over the whole experimental period show that nitrogen use efficiency, including biological nitrogen fixation, was above 85% for all systems. Organic systems covered nitrogen export of crops due to nitrogen fixation by legumes in the rotation, and the amount of fixed nitrogen exceeded the fertilizer nitrogen. Organic fertilization with farmyard manure at 14. LU ha⁻¹ maintained or raised soil carbon and nitrogen stocks on the long term, with an increase in systems with manure compost, and a decrease with exclusively mineral fertilizers. Soil based climate impact was mainly driven by N₂O emissions and was 56% lower per hectare in organic systems in a measurement period covering grass-clover, maize, and green-manure. Organic cropping systems showed enhanced soil quality, and richness of micro- and macrofauna. Despite a rigorous reduction of inputs yields of the organic systems achieved 85% of the conventional systems. Highest yield gap was observed for potato, followed by wheat, maize, and grass clover, while similar yields were observed for soya.

³¹ Mäder et al., 2002.

LL2 Challenges to be addressed

The Living Lab goals are:

- To improve carbon sequestration and soil fertility in arable soils by increasing humus content.
- To improve yield stability by increasing water holding capacity.
- To introduce and test the impact-based compensation system for the increase of SOM.
- To assess the potentials of IR spectroscopy to measure SOM and allow in-field advisory services.

Potential Activities/Interventions

The measures will be discussed individually on each farm and can include, for example:

- Year-round soil coverage
- Crop residues: retention, recycling, incorporation.
- Organic fertilizer: manure, slurry, compost, digestate, pomace.
- Balanced and diverse crop rotation.
- Reduced tillage.
- Ground cover in orchards and vineyards.
- Hedges, field copses, agroforestry.
- Biochar application to soils.

Monitoring & Impact

All 705 plots on 55 farms are sampled and analysed for SOC stocks in the 1st, 3rd and 6th year of the project.

50 plots of the 10 focus farms are sampled and analysed every year during the whole project duration, as well as analysed for SOC stocks and further characteristics of SOC dynamics. In addition, GIS studies on natural and socio-economical driving factors of SOC dynamics are continuously monitored. IR spectroscopy is continuously evaluated as a rapid, cheap, and precise monitoring tool for SOC dynamics in the lab and field (MRV for carbon compensation projects). The focus farms are also monitored for the effects of the interventions on yield stability and biodiversity.

All 55 farms in the LL are contributing to annual project meetings, and 20 farms are part of a working group on soil organic matter and meet monthly. There is also vivid and regular exchange with two other compensation/climate mitigation projects in Switzerland, as well as loose exchanges with other cantonal soil management projects.

Figure 34. LL2 intervention process and monitoring

Stakeholder identification, mapping and engagement

Introduction to methodology

Stakeholder identification and mapping is a crucial step to understand and address the various stakeholders that will be involved during InBestSoil lifetime and beyond. Through this process, the project aims to identify and analyse the key actors who may impact or be impacted by the project: by understanding their roles, interests, and needs, we can establish effective communication, foster strong collaborations, and make informed decisions that promote the success and sustainability of InBestSoil, as well as to facilitate the co-creation tasks within the project.

As described in the previous section, InBestSoil counts with representatives from 7 Lighthouses (LH) and 2 Living Labs (LL) in its consortium, in order to ensure access to the different case studies and effectively deliver on project results, including a diverse stakeholder profile network.

In order to conduct a preliminary Stakeholder identification and mapping, LH and LL representatives in the Consortium provided direct information about stakeholders they believe are important to engage with in each case study, whether they are in contact with them or not. This approach helped to capture a preliminary wide spectrum of stakeholders who may impact or be impacted by the project and provides an initial overview of the stakeholders that need to be involved in InBestSoil.

During this exercise, various aspects for each stakeholder were analysed such as their profile, nature of their activity, contact details as well as their preferred communication means and format. This information will help determine the specific role they might play as stakeholders in the project and beyond and establish effective ways of communication to foster productive relationships within the project lifetime.

In essence, this stakeholder identification and mapping exercise offered InBestSoil an initial glimpse into the stakeholders' profiles and potential needs and interest points that might increase their interest to engage with the project.

Figure 35. InBestSoil stakeholder engagement approach.

InBestSoil steps for Stakeholder engagement

The relationship between projects and their stakeholders usually has a progressive evolution. InBestSoil aims to evolve from the identification and mapping of stakeholders to phases where they can be involved in decision making processes (WP3-WP4), including strategies and policies (WP5-WP6):

Figure 36. InBestSoil engagement scope.

InBestSoil will follow 5 steps to engage with its stakeholders in the LH and LL included in the project but also, with external stakeholders such as sister projects and other Mission Soil projects including umbrella projects PREPSOIL and NATI00NS, EU wide initiatives (EUSO etc.) and international experts as needed.

Figure 37. InBestSoil engagement steps.

Analysis and mapping of stakeholders

The analysis and mapping of stakeholders will ensure that a sufficient, diverse, and meaningful representation and participation of stakeholders is included in the delivery of project results. By identifying key stakeholders, InBestSoil will consider the input and feedback from these groups of interest from early stages of the solutions development process ensuring a better understanding and integration of these approaches in the different soil types and land uses represented in the project.

The steps that InBestSoil will follow to analyse and map its key stakeholders are:

1. **Pre-identification** of stakeholders (M8): In this case a pre-identification of main local stakeholders has been carried out for each LH and LL but also, outside the project. These stakeholders are considered to potentially have an impact on or be impacted by the project.
2. **Characterization** of stakeholders (M8-M18), in order to understand their priorities and motivations.
3. **Mapping** stakeholders (M18): InBestSoil will develop a map of all the stakeholders identified ranged according to the impact they have in the project and the impact they

may perceive from the project. To develop the map, the following questions have been posed:

- Have all stakeholders related to InBestSoil been identified?
- Who are the stakeholders who have the most influence on the project?
- Who are the stakeholders that will be more affected by the project?
- Which are the motivations and interests of the stakeholders concerning the project?

The map will be built using an impact matrix as follows:

Figure 38. Stakeholder engagement Impact matrix.

In the updated version of the deliverable, *D2.1 Pre-stakeholder mapping for LHs and LLs (M18)*, a needs assessment will be carried out to identify and prioritise the issues that are more important to partners and stakeholders.

Definition of the objective

Participation of key stakeholders in Mission Soil projects is essential to ensure the "Awareness of soil issues is key to ensuring active position/participation and involvement on the part of interested parties in activities and initiatives related to soil health"³².

The objective therefore is to inform, consult, involve, and collaborate with key stakeholders within the LH and LLs included in the project as well as external ones to ensure that project results meet and respond to real needs and challenges. Specifically, InBestSoil will engage with stakeholders to:

1. Co-defining SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS for each Ecosystem Service, responding to land users, managers and/or policymakers' priorities and needs (WP3)
2. To assess the benefits and barriers for CARBON FARMING and which measures would benefit land users (WP4)
3. Understanding which BUSINESS MODELS and INCENTIVES best support land users would and/or managers that decide to implement sustainable practices (WP5)

³² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Communication and citizen engagement initiatives in line with the Horizon Europe Mission A Soil Deal for Europe – Report on dissemination and exploitation practices in Member States and associated countries*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/704413>

shared by LH and LL representatives and all project partners to gather additional stakeholders.

Tools for engagement

There are many different methods and tools to engage with stakeholders. In this section the tools found to be more useful for InBestSoil have been described. These tools will be adapted to the needs, knowledge, and willingness of stakeholders to participate in the activities proposed and used as appropriate to effectively deliver on project results.

GENERAL TOOLS

Some of the general engagement tools that InBestSoil is planning to use are as follows:

- Surveys – Will be initially used to inform pre-identified stakeholders about InBestSoil and collect information about their willingness and interest to participate in upcoming engagement activities, as well as completing the needs analysis.
- Interviews – Once the mapping of key stakeholders has been developed based on the information gathered from the surveys, initial interviews will be organized with key stakeholders to inform about the engagement activities to be carried out, their expected role and any aspects they could benefit from during the process.
- Informative sessions / Workshops – Depending on the concerns and requirements identified during the surveys and interviews period, informative or co-creation sessions will be delivered to interested stakeholders. These sessions will be tailor made, taking into account both the needed participants and the topic, aiming at building a community of well informed and engaged stakeholders to contribute to the successful development of InBestSoil

Some tools for engagement have been already developed for this preliminary stakeholder identification and mapping process (See previous and next sections).

ONLINE ENGAGEMENT TOOLS

To understand the challenges and opportunities for engagement within each LH and LL, a collaborative digital whiteboard was created. This interactive tool serves as a collaborative space where they can provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities related to stakeholder engagement in their respective LHs and LLs.

The whiteboard includes specific questions such as identifying the main challenges faced when engaging stakeholders as well as potential challenging times for stakeholder engagement throughout each year of the project.

The whiteboard is titled "LH & LL Leaders" and has the objective: "To understand the challenges and opportunities for engagement in each LH and LL." It is divided into several sections:

- Main challenges identified to engage stakeholders:** A grid of pink boxes for identifying challenges.
- Identify potential challenging times for SE engagement:** A timeline for the years 2023, 2024, 2025, and 2026.
- Any ideas to improve the stakeholder engagement approach in future tasks?:** A grid of pink boxes for suggesting improvements.
- Which stakeholders from your LH/LL might find valuable/interesting the following project results?:** A grid of pink boxes for identifying stakeholders.
- Questions (E01-E11):** A large grid of questions with columns for "Challenges", "Opportunities", and "Willingness".

Figure 41. Online engagement tools example.

By understanding these aspects InBestSoil will tailor the communication and engagement efforts to effectively match stakeholders' interests and needs. Furthermore, LH and LL consortium partners have been encouraged to share their ideas for improving the stakeholder engagement approach in the future. By gathering these suggestions, InBestSoil will refine its engagement strategies and ensure continuous improvement, fostering stronger connections and collaborations with stakeholders.

INBESTSOIL DIGITAL COLLABORATION PLATFORM

Lastly, InBestSoil is developing its “collaboration platform” through *Task 2.4 Development and maintenance of InBestSoil a digital collaboration platform for LHs and LLs*. The platform aims at promoting the effective collaboration among LHs and LLs at regional, national and European level to support the development of business cases, ensure the further engagement with international stakeholders, and optimize the exchange of information within each LL and LH.

To achieve a collaborative definition of the platform functionalities, a Platform Committee composed of consortium members was established in M1. The Committee has had 6 workshops during the first 6 months of InBestSoil implementation to collectively go through all the functionalities of the platform.

A first version of the platform has been made available to the project consortium members to assess its usability and functionalities and provide feedback and recommendations back to the developers. Once this feedback is integrated, the platform will be made available to key project stakeholders for further testing.

Figure 42. First version of InBestSoil collaboration platform.

As a living platform, it will be updated and improved all along the project duration, benefit from new functionalities also coming from other EU projects that use the platform for equivalent purposes.

Among other functionalities, the platform features i) A common discussion and knowledge area to enable all stakeholders to build synergies and discuss topics in a transversal way across sectors and LHs/LLs; and ii) Specific communities with restricted access for each LL/LH to enable exchanges and information sharing within the community of stakeholders for each LL and LH

To maximise the impact of the platform, conversations with sister projects as well as key stakeholders have started to set up the first Working Groups by focus of interest. The **proposed Working Groups** so far are as follows:

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Exchange information about strategies to reach out to new stakeholders and about stakeholders already contacted or planned to be contacted. This group is designed to reduce stakeholder fatigue, i.e., to avoid contacting the same stakeholder numerous times.
- **Living Labs and Lighthouses:** Exchange information on LLs and LHs with other projects and collaborate with those in the same area.
- **Soil health indicators and testing procedures:** Several projects share tasks on defining soil health indicators, thus, a WG on the topic will be promoted.
- **Life cycle analysis and economic valuation:** Several projects share tasks on the topic of economic valorisation, thus, a WG on the topic will be promoted.
- **Soil health business models upscaling:** To study ways to scale up different business models (focused on carbon farming, for example), and the transition

towards regenerative agriculture models (from a social, economic, and environmental perspective).

- **New business models based on soil health:** A group to look at the different approaches used to establish new business models.
- **Incentive toolbox:** This working group has already started with the sister projects but can be extended to other mission projects.
- **Certification approaches and policy recommendations:** At the end, a report on this activity has to be written, and it would be better to condense the ideas from several projects (at least from the projects of the same call).
- **Communication and dissemination:** This group can be divided in two and used to exchange information about communication and dissemination events.

As the platform is in its initial stages, an update on its final configuration and working groups created including membership registry will be shared in the updated version of this deliverable (M18).

Monitoring and evaluation

The implementation of this engagement approach will contribute to the definition of the *D2.3 Co-design and co-creation plan for InBestSoil (M20)*, which will include all the objectives, activities, timeline, and monitoring of the co-creation activities to be carried out through the project lifetime to deliver on its planned results.

The present document will be a dynamic document which will be updated along with InBestSoil research findings and contributions to ensure that all stakeholders contributing or participating in the project are properly identified, categorised, and mapped.

Engagement satisfaction will be measured through the InBestSoil collaboration platform. The way in which this will be done is still to be defined once the platform is up and running. This information will be updated in the updated version of this deliverable by M18.

InBestSoil LH and LL stakeholder preliminary identification

During the first months of InBestSoil two streams related to stakeholder engagement have been primarily carried out:

- Preliminary analysis of potential stakeholders for each LH and LL which will continue until M18 to complete T2.1 Analysis and mapping of stakeholders for each LH and LL.
- First task completed in co-creation with stakeholders (T3.1) Co-definition of suitable indicators and standardized metrics for the LCA and evaluation of ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil in different land uses.

These two activities have been running in parallel in order to ensure a preliminary cohort of stakeholders to work with and kickstart the project.

To date, about n280 potential stakeholders have been identified through LH and LL coordinators (project partners representing each LH and LL).

Based on the information collected from LLs and LHs, an initial identification and distribution of stakeholder groups was carried out as presented below:

LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil - Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván (El Baldío) Stakeholder groups identified and classification

Currently, environmental organisations have the highest engagement with LH1, constituting 24% of the existing stakeholders with whom they have contact, followed closely by Academia (22%) and Public Bodies (20%). Despite their vital role in the work that is being done with LH1, farmers currently have a lower engagement rate (15%) compared to other stakeholders. Given the significance of farmers in the LH1's context, where agricultural practices play a pivotal role, it is essential to strengthen communication and engagement with them during the project's course.

Currently, there is also limited contact with the local community, accounting for only 11% of stakeholder engagement. During the project lifetime, efforts will be made to enhance relationships with local communities, putting particular emphasis on building stronger ties with the farming community.

LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil - Saelices el Chico old uranium mine

LH2 currently maintains connections primarily with industry (36%) and other project partners (22%). However, interactions with academia, environmental organisations, and the local community stand at a relatively lower 14% each.

Considering the restoration efforts undertaken to mitigate the impacts of the former uranium mine, and all the relevant information and expertise that has been generated due to the work carried out in the LH, there is a pertinent opportunity to strengthen ties with this with environmental organisations and academia specially, as well as to reach out to the local community.

Additionally, during the project scope, partnerships with Local Action Groups in Salamanca could be explored, such as the Association for the Development of Ciudad Rodrigo (ADECOCIR) and the Association for the Development of the Western Zone of Salamanca (ADEZOS), among other relevant groups. These local associations may offer support and resources to reinforce their activities, ensuring a comprehensive and well-rounded approach to soil restoration in the region.

NOTE: LH2 is currently undergoing a process of management change, which may pose challenges in stakeholder engagement. During this transitional phase, full-fledged engagement may be limited. The project team anticipates resuming active engagement once the process is completed to ensure optimal project implementation.

Currently, LH3 has engagement primarily with Industry (25%) and Academia (25%). However, its interactions with other stakeholders are comparatively lower, especially in regard to environmental organisations (12%). Enhancing collaboration with these organisations could prove highly valuable and interesting, considering the LH3's expertise in improving soil health and the knowledge on techniques for doing so. By fostering increased engagement with environmental organisations, LH3 could spread its specialized knowledge and experience in soil remediation, could spread your information, useful for the objectives of this type of organisations and their objectives.

In addition to the existing stakeholders and given the specific characteristics of the lighthouse, LH3 has identified several key groups of interest that will receive focused engagement throughout the project, such as mining companies and technosols producers.

LH4. Continental Urban Soil – Peri-urban soils, Zagreb

LH4 currently maintains the highest level of contact and engagement with academia, constituting 34% of its engagement with stakeholders. Following closely are farmers and public organisations, each representing 25% of the contact. However, there is relatively lower engagement with the industry, accounting for 13% of stakeholders. Notably, the local community has the least engagement with the lighthouse, at just 4%. Considering the limited engagement with the local community efforts to increase contact and strengthen relationships with them will be made within the project scope.

LH4 will also prioritize keeping farmers engaged and establishing significant contact with them. This emphasis stems from the lighthouse's approach, which aims to address critical issues such as the absence of modern and sustainable agricultural practices in Zagreb. With the current practices relying on traditional methods passed down through generations, the project seeks to work closely with farmers to introduce innovative and environmentally friendly techniques, fostering long-term sustainable land use practices.

LH5. Boreal Urban Soil – Baltupiai urban gardens

LH5 primarily focuses its engagement efforts on landowners, representing 42% of its stakeholder interactions. This emphasis is reasonable considering the lighthouse's core focus on land management and sustainable practices. Additionally, it maintains a significant engagement of 33% with public bodies, fostering collaboration with relevant authorities and policymakers. While the engagement with environmental organisations stands at 17%, it remains valuable in leveraging their expertise and insights to address environmental concerns and ensure ecologically responsible land management.

In the context of the Baltupiai gardens, LH5 aims to undertake various engagement activities beyond sample collection. These activities include conducting surveys among farmers to assess their ecosystem services (cultural) and fostering collaboration with different stakeholders, such as the municipality, NGOs, farmers, and the Ministry of Environment and Agriculture.

The primary objective of LH5 is to address issues related to poor land use in Baltupiai gardens. Notably, one of the significant challenges is the prevailing use of agrochemicals by gardeners in land management, coupled with intensive production. Consequently, during the project, engagement with gardeners will be emphasized, seeking to work closely with them to introduce sustainable and environmentally friendly land use practices, mitigating the adverse impacts of agrochemical usage and promoting more balanced and ecologically responsible gardening practices.

LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil – Mežole, Latvia

Currently, LH6 has established contact with three specific stakeholder groups, namely: land managers, public bodies, and academia. Notably, the project exhibits significant engagement with academia, representing 41% of its stakeholders. This strong connection with academic institutions indicates a focus on research, knowledge exchange, and expertise integration to address land management challenges effectively.

As the project progresses, we will seek to expand its contact with additional stakeholder groups, to ensure a more comprehensive and inclusive approach in achieving its objectives. Having contact with stakeholder groups such as environmental organisations could hold considerable value for LH6, as these organisations often possess specialized expertise and insights into environmental conservation and sustainable land management practices.

LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil

LH7 currently establishes its strongest contact with farmers, accounting for 50% of its stakeholder engagement., which aligns with the Lighthouse's objective of promoting sustainable management practices that promote soil health and economic development.

Additionally, the Lighthouse also maintains contact with industry (23%), reflecting the importance of private sector involvement in sustainable land management initiatives. However, it has relatively limited engagement with environmental organisations (8%) and with academia and public bodies (4% each). Recognizing the significance of these

stakeholder groups in advancing sustainable practices, we aim to increase LL3's engagement with these stakeholder groups during the project lifetime.

While actively fostering stronger relationships with academia, public bodies, and environmental organisations, LL3 will also remain committed to maintaining its connection with farmers. By achieving a balanced and inclusive approach to stakeholder engagement, it seeks to reach its objective of promoting sustainable management practices that lead to enhanced soil health and economic development.>

LL 1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil - Grande Pianura del Campidano, la Nurra, la Gallura and other areas of Sardegna

LL1 already engages with various stakeholder groups, with the highest contact being with public bodies (39%), followed by farmers (28%), and academia (15%). The Living Lab's objective centres around implementing a conservation agriculture cropping system to enhance sustainability, soil fertility, and overall soil health, and to test conservation agriculture practices.

Throughout the project, LL1 will maintain contact with public bodies due to their crucial role in policy support and implementation, and ongoing engagement with farmers and academia will remain essential for effective project implementation and knowledge exchange. Furthermore, during the project, the Living Lab will try to strengthen its relationships relationship with industry (9%), CSOs (4%), and NGOs (2%), with whom there is currently limited engagement. By fostering closer ties with these stakeholder groups, we aim to ensure a comprehensive and collaborative approach to conservation agriculture practices, leading to improved sustainability and soil health.

LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil - Climate protection through humus build-up, Baselland Canton, Switzerland

LL2 establishes its primary relationship with farmers, accounting for a significant 46% of its stakeholder engagement. This reflects the Living Labs approach, whose goal is to adapt agriculture to climate change, bolstering soil resilience and fertility against extreme weather events, while also ensuring future food security. As a result, farmers receive critical guidance and advice on adopting sustainable agricultural practices that align with climate change adaptation strategies.

Additionally, LL2 foresees substantial collaboration with other project partners, comprising 38% of its stakeholder engagement. This partnership approach fosters knowledge exchange and resource-sharing, further reinforcing the project's objectives of climate-resilient agriculture and sustainable land management. However, it is worth noting that Living Lab currently has minimal engagement with industry and public bodies, representing only 8% of each group.

Despite the Living Lab's primary focus on farmers, closer collaboration with the industry and public bodies will also be important for successfully achieving its objectives. To address this, during the project lifetime, LL2 will strengthen its ties with these stakeholders.

Stakeholders interest preliminary assessment

Several discussions were carried out with all project partners in order to establish the most efficient way to carry out the stakeholders' preliminary identification for InBestSoil. These 280 pre-identified stakeholders were contacted via email with a short presentation (Annex I) of InBestSoil and an invitation to complete a survey where they could indicate their interest in participating in the project. From these contacts, 105 stakeholders have shown interest in participating in the project:

Figure 43. Distribution of stakeholder interest survey respondents by LH and LL.

As it is observed, the distribution of responses received varies between different LH and LL. This gives us an idea of where we should put more effort and find adequate communication channels to engage with stakeholders. However, interest from stakeholders from outside "InBestSoil" has also been identified which opens further opportunities for collaboration beyond the scope of the project too. As indicated in the previous section, LH2 is undergoing a process of management change which has affected their participation in the project, but the issue is expected to be fixed in the coming months and their participation resumed.

In relation to the respondent profiles, the distribution is also uneven. Most respondents were academics, farmers, and policymakers whereas more effort into engaging with industry and civil society organisations will need to be done. A graph with the profile distribution results is presented as follows:

NOTE: LL3 has been reclassified as LH7. It's important to note that during the time of the survey, LL3 was designated as such. This classification discrepancy will be rectified for all upcoming surveys, deliverables and activities related to the project.

Figure 44. Total distribution of profiles responding to the stakeholder interest survey.

When it comes to the communication channels to be used, most stakeholders prefer to be contacted via email although there is also a preference for face to face or online meetings, when possible.

Figure 45. Preferred communication channels of respondents to the stakeholder interest survey.

Finally, stakeholders preferred language was also sought most respondents being able to communicate in English, although a good number indicating that they would need to communicate in their local language.

Figure 46. Preferred language indicated by respondents in the stakeholder interest survey.

The stakeholder interest survey remains open for stakeholders to register their interest in participating in the project³³. All the **responses from the survey will be thoroughly analysed and taken into consideration when designing the co-creation activities** (D2.3. Co-design and co-creation plan for stakeholders).

³³ <https://forms.office.com/e/g653VrtMqi>

Preliminary barriers and challenges related to stakeholder engagement

There are a number of barriers and challenges that have been identified in relation to stakeholder engagement during this preliminary process of stakeholder identification and mapping phase. These barriers have been collected in this document to be taken into consideration when progressing with project tasks. Measures taken to minimise the impact of the challenges below will be recorded in the updated version of this deliverable in M18 and, in D2.3. Co-design and co-creation plan for stakeholders in M20 for those barriers specifically concerning co-creation activities.

- InBestSoil started in January 2023 and this deliverable was due in August 2023 (M8). Project partners and LH and LL stakeholders had issues related to workload that impacted their contribution to the project. For example, the end of each trimester is usually complicated for most businesses, since they have to close the accounts for the trimester, and planting/seeding season (December-January) and harvesting season (April-June) are difficult times to engage farmers. August and December are complicated periods for policymakers, due to summer and winter holiday times, and "school" periods are complicated for academics due to the volume of work they might have.
- Engaging with stakeholders in a face-to-face basis has been complicated but being the preference for some of the stakeholders, the project will work on ways to improve this engagement format.
- LH2 is undergoing a process of management change which has affected their participation in the project, but the issue is expected to be fixed in the coming months and their participation resumed.
- Sometimes there is little to no connection between the companies involved in the LL/LH and other social agents that we want to engage with the project. Therefore, the project will work on improving these connections.
- Some LL/LH don't have many stakeholders directly involved in their daily activities. For example: LH3 involves the remediation of many soils, so most stakeholders are inter-related companies.
- Stakeholders could lose interest in participating in project activities along the project duration.
- Decision makers could have a short amount of time to participate in engagement activities.

When carrying out engagement activities with stakeholders, it should also be considered that there are times of the year when, due to the characteristics of stakeholder groups, it will be more difficult to maintain active contact. Therefore, InBestSoil will implement co-creation activities adapted to stakeholders needs during these periods.

Conclusions

This first approach to the context of each Living Labs (LL) and Lighthouses (LH) involved in InBestSoil, and the preliminary identification and mapping of the different stakeholder groups and structure of the engagement strategy has led us to detect areas for improvement that will be developed further in upcoming project activities.

This deliverable presents the preliminary findings of the Stakeholder Identification mapping and engagement process conducted for the InBestSoil project. The document provides a general context of all the LL and LH involved in the project, outlines the methodology used for mapping and engaging stakeholders, and presents the initial results obtained from this exercise.

The preliminary stakeholder identification and mapping process involved gathering information from LL and LH representatives, has led to collect valuable insights regarding stakeholders with whom they already have established connections and those they consider important for future relationships. Having these pre-relationships created is very useful for projects such as InBestSoil with large numbers of case studies and partners involved.

Based on the data collected, an initial stakeholder identification and mapping has been created, providing a broad overview of the stakeholders involved in the InBestSoil project. This mapping offers valuable insights into the diverse range of stakeholders, their roles, and their potential interest in the project's objectives and results. This serves as a foundation for effective engagement, communication, and collaboration with these stakeholders throughout the project's lifespan which will be outlined in detail in *D2.3. Co-design and co-creation plan for stakeholders*.

It is important to note that this document represents a preliminary snapshot of the stakeholder landscape and will be updated and refined as the project progresses. An updated version will be submitted in M18. As further engagement activities take place and new stakeholders are identified, the stakeholder mapping will be reviewed and updated.

Annex I

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